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PHD THESIS

NONPARAMETRIC SIMULTANEOUS CONFIDENCE BANDS WITH PALEY-WIENER KERNELS

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Abstract

The thesis introduces nonparametric methods to construct simultaneous confidence bands for band-limited functions from a finite sample of input-output pairs, based on the theory of Paley-Wiener reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. If the distribution function of the inputs is a priori known, the constructed bands provide nonasymptotic guarantees for the inclusion of the true regression function, simultaneously for all possible inputs, otherwise, the results are asymptotic. In both cases, the confidence bands are strongly uniformly consistent. The proposed algorithm is also demonstrated on single image inpainting and super-resolution problems, providing simultaneous, nonasymptotic confidence bands for the missing pixel values, next to the point estimates. Several numerical experiments are implemented to support the feasibility of the introduced approaches.

Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
a.e.	almost everywhere
a.s.	almost surely
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, Key / Black
EDSR	Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution
flop	floating point operation
GP	Gaussian Process
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression
i.i.d.	independent and identically distributed
KDE	Kernel Density Estimation
KGP	Kernel Gradient Perturbation
KRR	Kernel Ridge Regression
LS	Least Squares
LSE	Least Squares Estimation
ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MSRN	Multi-Scale Residual Network
NN	Nearest Neighbor
NRMSE	Normalized Root Mean Square Error
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-noise Ratio
PW	Paley-Wiener
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
RKHS	Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space
SGKI	Simultaneously Guaranteed Kernel Interpolation
SPS	Sign-Perturbed Sums
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
w.l.o.g.	without the loss of generality
w.r.t.	with respect to

Notations

Analysis

$\mathbb{I}(x)$	the indicator function
$\Pi(x)$	the rectangular function
$\mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{X})$	the set of square-integrable functions on a measure space \mathbb{X}
$\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{Y})$	the set of functions from the nonempty set \mathbb{X} to \mathbb{Y}
$\frac{\partial}{\partial s}$	partial derivative according to variable s

Linear Algebra

$A \in F^{m \times n}$	a matrix with m rows and n columns over the field F
A^T	the transpose of matrix A
$\det(A)$	the determinant of matrix A
I_n	the identity matrix with dimension n
$A \succeq 0$	matrix A is positive semidefinite
$\begin{bmatrix} A_1 & A_2 \\ A_3 & A_4 \end{bmatrix}$	block matrix

Probability and Mathematical Statistics

Ω	the set of elementary events
\mathcal{J}	σ -algebra of subsets of Ω
\mathbb{P}	a probability measure on (Ω, \mathcal{J})
$\mathbb{P}(A)$	the probability of event A
$\mathbb{P}(A B)$	the conditional probability of event A conditioned on event B
$\mathbb{P}(A \mathcal{J})$	the conditional probability of A conditioned on σ -algebra \mathcal{J}
$\mathbb{E}[X]$	the expected value of random variable X
$\mathbb{E}[X A]$	the conditional expected value of random variable X conditioned on event A

$\mathbb{E}[X \mathcal{J}]$	the conditional expected value of random variable X conditioned on sigma-algebra \mathcal{J}
$\mathbb{V}[X]$	the variance of random variable X
$\text{Cov}(X)$	the covariance of a random vector X
$X \sim Z$	the random variable X is distributed according to Z
$\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$	multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ
$\stackrel{\text{d}}{=}$	equality in distribution
$\xrightarrow{\text{d}}$	convergence in distribution
$\xrightarrow{\text{p}}$	convergence in probability
$\xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}}$	almost sure convergence

Introduced Notation

f_*	the data-generating function
θ^*	the true regression parameter
m	number of observations on the prototype sample
n	number of observations on the labeled data set
$\{x_k\}_{k=1}^n$	the set of inputs from the labeled data set
$\{x'_k\}_{k=1}^m$	the set of inputs from the (unlabeled) prototype sample
$\{y_k\}_{k=1}^n$	the set of outputs from the labeled data set
$\{\varepsilon_k\}_{k=1}^n$	the set of noise terms from the labeled data set
\mathcal{D}'_m	the prototype sample
\mathcal{Z}_n	the labeled data set
h_*	the density function of the labeled inputs
\mathcal{H}	the Hilbert space of choice
K	Gram matrix of the labeled inputs
K_0	the Gram matrix extended with query input x_0
d	the dimension of the inputs
n_0	the number of chosen data points for the KGP method
$[n]$	the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$
\hat{f}_n	the minimum norm interpolant of the labeled data set
\hat{h}_m	the kernel density estimation of h_*
$f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n$	function f interpolates the data set \mathcal{Z}_n

Introduction

Extracting valuable information from datasets has become an essential task with the technological advancements of our time. Machine learning (ML) is a field which aims to learn from empirical data, in order to generalize those results in an automated way, to support efficient prediction and decision making. There are many real-world application domains of ML, such as healthcare [1, 2, 3], social networks [4, 5, 6], search engines [7, 8, 9], industry [10, 11, 12] and finance [13, 14, 15]. The term itself was first introduced in 1959 by Arthur Samuel [16], and ML has many connections with mathematical statistics. Some scholars even treat ML as a part of statistics. For example, Robert Tibshinari, a professor of statistics at the Stanford University, who is known for the LASSO regularization method [17, 18], called machine learning “glorified statistics”. Another example is Michael Jordan, a professor of statistics at the University of California, Berkeley, who mentioned that “I don’t make the distinction between statistics and machine learning [...]”

Regression is one of the fundamental problems of mathematical statistics, system identification, signal processing and machine learning [19]. When a finite sample of input-output pairs is given, the general aim is to estimate the so-called *regression function*, which, given an input, encodes the conditional expectation of the corresponding output [20]. There are several well-known (parametric and nonparametric) approaches for regression [21, 22], from linear regression to neural networks [23, 24, 25] and kernel methods [26, 27, 28], which provide *point-estimates* from a given model class [29]. However, sole point-estimates are often not sufficient and *region-estimates* are also needed, for example, for *risk management* and to support *robust* decision making.

Confidence regions constitute a standard statistical approach to region estimation. They have a rich history and they are strongly connected to the theory of statistical hypothesis testing: famous historical results include the development of the χ^2 test from Karl Pearson [30] and the work of Ronald Fisher [31]. The connection comes from the fact that the acceptance region of a hypothesis test can be treated as a confidence region. Historically, Jerzy Neyman developed the main ideas in the 1930s [32, 33, 34]. Erich Leo Lehmann also worked with nonparametric confidence intervals for a parameter, which can be obtained from the Wilcoxon test [35]. The historic Statistical Methods book of George

Snedecor [36] also included confidence intervals in a later edition with the contribution of William Gemmill Cochran [37]. Confidence intervals, a special case of confidence regions, have also been widely used in practice, for example, in medicine [38, 39].

A well-known and powerful methodology to construct point as well as region estimations is given by *Gaussian process regression* [40, 41]. These algorithms are based on Bayesian statistics [42, 43] and, besides point estimates, they can provide prediction regions for the outputs and credible regions for the expected outputs [44]. While these methods provide computationally efficient solutions, the rather strong Gaussianity assumption can sometimes prove to be unrealistic. A more detailed theoretical description of Gaussian process regression, for the cases of noise-free and noisy observations, together with its connection to Kernel Ridge Regression [45, 46] is given in Chapter 4. While the assumptions behind this methodology are rather strong, they can be relaxed in many ways. One of the examples include the usage of quantile regression [47].

In case we consider linearly parametrized models, a promising, new approach to build confidence regions for the fixed “true” model parameters, has been given by the so-called *Sign-Perturbed Sums (SPS)* method [48]. This algorithm provides nonasymptotic solutions with exact coverage probabilities under mild statistical assumptions, which include the independence and the symmetricity of the noise terms without assuming any other a priori knowledge. Next to the finite sample coverage guarantees, by adding some mild assumptions, the method also becomes strongly uniformly consistent [49]. The core ideas and the main theoretical results of SPS are summarized in Chapter 1.

A fairly new result with a deterministic setting was provided in [50]. The core assumptions of that approach are as follows. We know upper bounds for the noise terms and for the kernel norm of the true regression function, which comes from a Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space (RKHS). This method uses the properties of *minimum norm interpolants* in RKHSs [27]. The uncertainty bounds for the value of the regression function at any input point, except for the observed ones, are obtained by solving two convex optimization problems. The width of these *uncertainty envelopes* is always smaller than the assumed noise bound, and it also holds true that obtaining more observations can only reduce the uncertainty. A detailed description of RKHSs and these minimum norm interpolants, which we will also exploit in our construction, is given in Chapter 3.

Providing prediction regions for the next (noisy) observation has many known solutions. *Interval Predictor Models* [51] are based on the scenario approach: in [52], a universal solution is provided under mild statistical assumptions. It is proven that the reliability of the minimax layer provided by the method follows Beta distribution, and this distribution is independent of the distribution behind the observations. By using this result, it is possible to quantify the exact reliability of the provided minimax layers for

any finite sample case without any a priori knowledge of the data generation process.

Another important framework is given by *conformal prediction*, which ensures finite sample levels of confidence by using past experience [53]. For an user-chosen significance level, by using any algorithm, which provides a prediction for a given variable, the method creates a set, which contains the predicted variable with a probability according to the user-chosen parameter. The only core assumption is the exchangeability of the data, which is satisfied in many standard problems and it is usually assumed when studying, e.g., neural networks [54], nearest neighbors methods [55] and random forests [56].

In [57], a new method is suggested for constructing distribution-free, nonparametric prediction bands for nonparametric regression. The approach combines the idea of conformal prediction with nonparametric conditional density estimation and it provides finite sample guarantees. The estimator also converges to an oracle band, the band one would use if the joint distribution would be known, under certain regularity conditions, which include a Lipschitz assumption for the conditional density.

A recent approach for achieving uncertainty quantification and constructing confidence sets with guaranteed coverage rates is provided in [58], which is also closely related to conformal prediction. The motivation is to “mimick” the original observed sample. These artificial samples are called *repro samples*, and one of their main advantage is that they do not rely on large sample central limit theorem and they are likelihood-free.

In this thesis, unlike most aforementioned methods, we focus on building confidence bands for the true regression function (instead of, e.g., building prediction regions for the next noisy observation). Even though in a parametric setting such region estimates are induced by the confidence sets in the parameter space, this approach is not feasible in nonparametric settings, which calls for direct constructions. Here, we suggest a nonparametric approach based on Paley-Wiener kernels. The algorithm can be used to construct data-driven confidence bands for an unknown, band-limited function, based on an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) sample of input-output pairs. The method is distribution-free in the sense that only mild statistical assumptions are required. The restriction to band-limited functions is a common and physically meaningful choice, as it inherently limits the function’s spectral content and thus its maximum rate of change.

The structure of the thesis is as follows. The first part, Part I, presents the core theoretical concepts underpinning the thesis. In Chapter 1, we provide a short description of linear regression, the least squares estimate, and the Sign-Perturbed Sums (SPS) method, which is able to construct nonasymptotic confidence regions with exact coverage guarantees, for symmetric noise term. In Chapter 2, the Fourier Transform and its inverse is described with the basic properties of the transformation. The Paley-Wiener spaces are also defined there. Chapter 3 gives an introduction to Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

(RKHSs) along with Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR). In Chapter 4, a brief overview is given for Gaussian Process Regression and its connection to KRR is discussed.

The new scientific contributions of the thesis are provided in Part II. In Chapter 5, we describe the problem setting we consider, which includes the data generation process, the objectives and the main assumptions. Then, using the SPS method, we introduce an approach which is able to build confidence bands for the case of finite dimensional model classes, and it can also build confidence intervals at the (observed) sample inputs for the general case. Finally, we give an overview of our general nonparametric construction. Chapter 6 describes the method to construct confidence bands for the regression function in the case when the distribution behind the inputs is assumed to be a priori known. First, we examine the case when the outputs are observed noise-free, then we generalize the result for the noisy case. Next to the coverage guarantee of the confidence bands, we also prove that the methods are strongly uniformly consistent, which means that as the sample size increases, they almost surely shrink around the true regression function. Then, we provide an alternative method to improve the computational complexity of the algorithms. In Chapter 7, the previous results are generalized for the case when the input distribution is unknown, by using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE). In this case, the coverage probabilities of the confidence bands become only asymptotically guaranteed, but they still remain strongly uniformly consistent. Finally, in Chapter 8, we demonstrate an application of these ideas to image processing problems, specifically single image inpainting and super-resolution. The results are illustrated by several qualitative and quantitative numerical experiments, located in Chapters 6, 7 and 8.

Part I

Theoretical Background

Chapter 1

Sign-Perturbed Sums (SPS)

We start the discussion of the theoretical background needed for the thesis with the Sign-Perturbed Sums (SPS) method, as it will be an important building block of our construction. SPS can build non-asymptotic confidence regions with exact coverage guarantees for the true parameters of linear regression problems, under mild statistical assumptions. A description of SPS, consisting the general idea, its main theoretical guarantees and the ellipsoidal approximation algorithm is presented here, based on [48].

In Section 5.5, we will describe a modified version of SPS which can construct guaranteed confidence intervals for the regression function at a given subset of the observed inputs. Later, this result will be used for the case when the outputs are observed with measurement noise. First, we will construct a guaranteed upper bound for the norm of the original regression function, then these SPS style confidence intervals will be used for building confidence intervals at any out-of-sample (non-observed) query input point.

1.1 Linear Regression

First, we provide a brief overview of the standard theory of linear regression. We consider the following data-generating system, for $k \in [n] \doteq \{1, \dots, n\}$:

$$y_k \doteq \varphi_k^T \theta^* + \varepsilon_k,$$

where $y_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is the (random) output, $\varepsilon_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is the (random) noise term, $\varphi_k \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the (deterministic) regressor, and $\theta^* \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the constant true system parameter, which needs to be estimated. For a finite setting, we consider a dataset (sample) that consists of outputs y_1, \dots, y_n and regressors $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n$. For simplicity, now we consider deterministic regressors, but the results can be easily generalized to i.i.d. regressors that are independent of the noises, as well (e.g., by simply conditioning on the regressors).

1.2 Basic Assumptions

The assumptions behind the SPS method are the following:

S1 *The noise terms, $\{\varepsilon_k\}$, are independent random variables and each ε_k has a symmetric probability distribution about zero.*

S2 *The regressors are deterministic and $\det(R_n) \neq 0$, where*

$$R_n \doteq \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T.$$

The strongest assumption for the noise terms is their independence, but it is standard in many statistical and machine learning works. We note that they do not have to be identically distributed. Another assumption is their symmetricity, which can be satisfied by many distributions, e.g., (zero mean) Gaussian, Laplace, Student t, uniform, Bernoulli, etc. We emphasize that the knowledge of the particular distribution is not assumed.

1.3 Least Squares Estimate

To find the Least Squares Estimate (LSE), the following predictors are introduced:

$$\hat{y}_k(\theta) \doteq \varphi_k^T \theta.$$

For a given θ , the prediction errors or residuals are defined by

$$\varepsilon_k(\theta) \doteq y_k - \hat{y}_k(\theta) = y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta.$$

The LSE is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squared errors, namely:

$$\hat{\theta}_n \doteq \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} \sum_{k=1}^n \varepsilon_k^2(\theta) = \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} \sum_{k=1}^n (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta)^2.$$

The solution is given by the normal equation (obtained by differentiating the objective):

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k(\theta) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta) = 0.$$

Under standard assumptions ensuring invertibility, such as assumption S2, the normal equation has an analytic solution, that is

$$\hat{\theta}_n = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k y_k \right).$$

1.4 Asymptotic Confidence Regions

Before we present the construction of SPS, we first recall the standard textbook approach for constructing confidence ellipsoids for the true parameters of linear regression models based on the sublevel sets of the limiting distribution of the scaled estimation errors.

If the $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ noise terms are i.i.d; have zero mean, finite variance, and the regressors are bounded, then $\sqrt{n}(\hat{\theta}_n - \theta^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, \Gamma)$, where \xrightarrow{d} denotes convergence in distribution. If σ^2 is the variance of the noise, then $\Gamma \doteq \sigma^2 R^{-1}$, and R is the limit of $R_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^\top$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ assuming this limit exists and is positive definite. From this, it follows that

$$\frac{n}{\sigma^2} (\hat{\theta}_n - \theta)^\top R_n (\hat{\theta}_n - \theta) \xrightarrow{d} \chi^2(d^*),$$

where $\chi^2(d^*)$ denotes the χ^2 distribution with $d^* \doteq \dim(\theta^*)$ degrees of freedom. By replacing (estimating) R with R_n and σ^2 with the unbiased estimate

$$\hat{\sigma}_n^2 \doteq \frac{1}{n - d^*} \sum_{k=1}^n \varepsilon_k^2(\hat{\theta}_n),$$

an approximate confidence region can be constructed as

$$\tilde{\Theta}_n \doteq \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq \frac{\mu \hat{\sigma}_n^2}{n} \right\},$$

where the $\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \tilde{\Theta}_n)$ is approximately $F_{\chi^2(d^*)}(\mu)$, where $F_{\chi^2(d^*)}$ is the cumulative distribution function of the χ^2 distribution with d^* degrees of freedom. That is, if we want to construct an $1 - \alpha$ level confidence set, we should use $\mu = F_{\chi^2(d^*)}^{-1}(1 - \alpha)$.

The confidence set constructed by this standard method only comes with asymptotic guarantees, for finite samples it can only be used as an approximate confidence set.

1.5 Finite Sample Properties

Now, we turn to the SPS method. We start by describing one of the intuitive ideas behind SPS. The normal equation (of the LSE) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^\top \tilde{\theta}_n + \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k = 0,$$

where $\tilde{\theta}_n \doteq \theta^* - \hat{\theta}_n$. The core idea for constructing the confidence regions comes from the fact that, assuming the regressors are deterministic, the uncertainty in the LSE comes from the noise terms $\{\varepsilon_k\}$. If the noises were zero, we would have $\hat{\theta}_n = \theta^*$. To obtain a confidence region, the method aims to evaluate the uncertainty of the estimate. By

assuming the symmetricity of the noise terms, $m - 1$ *sign-perturbed-sums* are introduced:

$$H_i(\theta) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \alpha_{i,k} (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta) = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta} + \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k \varepsilon_k,$$

where $i = 1, \dots, m - 1$ and $\{\alpha_{i,k}\}$ are i.i.d. Rademacher random variables that take on values ± 1 with probability $1/2$, respectively. Hence, the sign of the prediction errors in the normal equation is perturbed. For a given parameter θ , one can calculate the value of the case when no perturbation is used, namely:

$$H_0(\theta) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta} + \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k,$$

where H_0 will be called the *reference sum*. In the case of $\theta = \theta^*$, these sums are

$$H_0(\theta^*) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k,$$

$$H_i(\theta^*) = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k \varepsilon_k = \sum_{k=1}^n \pm \varphi_k \varepsilon_k,$$

where in the last sum, \pm is written instead of $\alpha_{i,k}$. Since the noise terms are independent and symmetric, $H_0(\theta^*)$ and $H_i(\theta^*)$ have the same distribution for any $i = 1, \dots, m - 1$. Furthermore, despite that they are dependent, one can prove that the probability that a given $\|H_j(\theta^*)\|^2$ is the k th largest one when ordering every single $\{\|H_i(\theta^*)\|^2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ is the same for every j including $j = 0$. This means that this probability is exactly $1/m$. In the case of “large enough” $\|\tilde{\theta}\|$, the following inequality holds with “high probability”:

$$\left\| \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta} + \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k \right\|^2 > \left\| \sum_{k=1}^n \pm \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta} + \sum_{k=1}^n \pm \varphi_k \varepsilon_k \right\|^2,$$

and the term $\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta}$ on the left side increases faster than $\sum_{k=1}^n \pm \varphi_k \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta}$ on the right side. Therefore, for large enough $\|\tilde{\theta}\|$ values, $\|H_0(\theta)\|^2$ dominates in the ordering of $\{\|H_i(\theta)\|^2\}$. The idea of the algorithm will come from these intuitions: the confidence region is constructed based on the rankings of the functions $\{\|H_i(\theta)\|^2\}$ and the θ parameters for which $\|H_0(\theta)\|^2$ dominates the other functions are left out.

Note that in the formal description of the SPS method, functions $\{\|H_i(\theta)\|\}$ are modified by an additional term, namely matrix $R_n^{-1/2}$, which helps to shape the confidence region, and an $1/n$ factor is also used to increase the numerical stability of the approach. Therefore, function $S_i(\theta) \doteq R_n^{-1/2} \frac{1}{n} H_i(\theta)$ is used instead of $H_i(\theta)$ in Algorithm 1. This, however, does not change the core idea of the construction.

The SPS method is based on two parts. The first part, which is called the initialization, sets the main global parameters and generates random objects which are required for

Algorithm 1 SPS-Initialization

- 1: Given a rational confidence probability $p \in (0, 1)$, set integers $l > q > 0$ such that $p = 1 - q/l$.
- 2: Calculate the outer product

$$R_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^T,$$

and find a factor $R_n^{1/2}$ such that

$$R_n^{1/2} (R_n^{1/2})^T = R_n.$$

- 3: Generate $n(l-1)$ i.i.d. random signs $\{\alpha_{k,t}\}$ with

$$\mathbb{P}(\alpha_{k,t} = 1) = \mathbb{P}(\alpha_{k,t} = -1) = 1/2$$

for $i \in [l-1]$ and $k \in [n]$.

- 4: Generate a random permutation π of the set $\{0, \dots, l-1\}$, where each $l!$ permutations has the same $1/(l!)$ probability to be selected.
-

the construction. In this section, the user-chosen p probability is set. The second part evaluates an indicator function, which can be used for a certain parameter value θ in order to decide whether that certain value is included in the confidence region.

The permutation in Algorithm 1 is required to break ties and to decide which function $\|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ or $\|S_j(\theta)\|^2$ is larger. Given l real numbers $\{Z_i\}$, where $i = 0, \dots, l-1$, a strict total order \prec_π is defined as follows: $Z_j \prec_\pi Z_k$ if and only if $Z_j < Z_k$ or $Z_j = Z_k$ and $\pi(j) < \pi(k)$, where π is randomly (uniformly) chosen from the symmetric group.

Observation 1.5.1 *Since π is a bijection from $\{0, \dots, l-1\}$ to itself, therefore, for $k \neq j$, $\pi(k)$ and $\pi(j)$ are two different integers in $\{0, \dots, l-1\}$.*

The indicator function defined in Algorithm 1 can be used to decide whether a given θ is included in the confidence region. By this construction, the p -level SPS confidence region can be defined as follows:

Definition 1.5.1 (p-level SPS confidence region) *For a given $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the p -level SPS confidence region is the following set:*

$$\hat{\Theta}_n \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \text{SPS-INDICATOR}(\theta) = 1\}.$$

Observation 1.5.2 *The Least Squares (LS) estimate, $\hat{\theta}_n$ has the property that $S_0(\hat{\theta}_n) = 0$ by definition. Therefore, the LS estimate is always included in the SPS confidence region, assuming that it is not empty.*

Algorithm 2 SPS-Indicator (θ)

1: For the given θ , compute the prediction errors for $k \in [n]$:

$$\varepsilon_k(\theta) \doteq y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta.$$

2: Evaluate

$$S_0(\theta) \doteq R_n^{-1/2} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varepsilon_k(\theta),$$

$$S_i(\theta) \doteq R_n^{-1/2} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k \varepsilon_k(\theta),$$

for $i \in [l-1]$.

3: Order the values $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|^2\}$ according to \prec_π .

4: Compute the rank $\mathcal{R}(\theta)$ of $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$ in the ordering of $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|^2\}$, where $\mathcal{R}(\theta) = 1$ if $\{\|S_0(\theta)\|^2\}$ is the smallest in the ordering, $\mathcal{R}(\theta) = 2$ if $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$ is the second smallest, and so on.

5: Return 1 if $\mathcal{R}(\theta) \leq l - q$. Otherwise, return 0.

Next, the theoretical guarantee of the method is summarized [48, Theorem 1].

Theorem 1.5.1 (SPS, exact coverage) *Assuming S1 and S2, for any given rational confidence probability $p \in (0, 1)$ it holds that*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n) = 1 - \frac{q}{l} = p,$$

where $m > q > 0$ are integers such that $p = 1 - q/l$.

Next to the confidence guarantee, the following theorem states that the SPS regions are built around the Least Squares estimate more precisely. First, we define star convexity.

Definition 1.5.2 (Star convexity) *A set $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ is called star convex if there is a star center $c \in \mathbb{R}^d$, such that*

$$\forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \forall \beta \in [0, 1] : \beta x + (1 - \beta)c \in \mathcal{X}.$$

Remark 1.5.1 *All convex sets are star convex, but the converse is not true.*

In the case of $q = 1$, the SPS region is the union of ellipsoids and it is generally not convex. The next theorem states, that even though this is true, the SPS regions are star convex [48, Theorem 2].

Theorem 1.5.2 (SPS, star convexity) *Assuming S1 and S2, the SPS confidence regions are star convex and the LS estimate is a star center.*

1.6 Strong Consistency

In this section, we will discuss an important attribute of the confidence regions provided by the method [49]. By adding some (mild) assumptions, the confidence regions will get smaller as the number of data points become larger. Next to that, if both the parameters n and m tend to infinity, the confidence regions will be contained in marginally inflated versions of confidence ellipsoids, which are obtained by asymptotic results.

The required additional assumptions are listed.

S3 (Non-vanishing excitation)

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{\min}(R_n) = \bar{\lambda} > 0,$$

where $\lambda_{\min}(\cdot)$ denotes the minimum eigenvalue.

S4 (Regressor growth rate restriction)

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\|\varphi_k\|^4}{k^2} < \infty.$$

S5 (Noise variance growth rate restriction)

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_k^2])^2}{k^2} < \infty.$$

The next theorem states that the $\hat{\Theta}_n$ confidence regions will eventually be included in any θ^* -centered norm-ball [49, Theorem 2].

Theorem 1.6.1 (Uniform strong consistency) *Assuming S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5 for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there almost surely exists an \bar{N} such that $\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq B_\varepsilon(\theta^*)$ for all $n > \bar{N}$.*

Theorem 1.6.1 states that the SPS algorithm is strongly consistent in the following sense: as the sample size increases, the constructed confidence sets shrink around the true parameter, and any other $\theta' \neq \theta^*$ is eventually excluded.

Next to the strong consistency, with some modified assumptions, the SPS confidence regions asymptotically have similar shapes to the standard confidence ellipsoids. The additional required assumptions are the following:

S6 (Regressor growth rate restriction)

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \|\varphi_k\|^4 < \infty.$$

S7 (i.i.d. noises with bounded 4th moments) $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ is i.i.d. with $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_k^4] = \rho < \infty$.

The theorem, which provides the asymptotic result is for the *relaxed asymptotic confidence ellipsoids*. These sets are defined as

$$\tilde{\Theta}_n(\varepsilon) \doteq \left\{ \theta : (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq \frac{\mu\sigma^2 + \varepsilon}{n} \right\},$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a margin, and $\sigma^2 \doteq \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_k^2]$ [49, Theorem 3].

Theorem 1.6.2 *Assuming S1, S2, S3, S6 and S7, there exists a double indexed set of variables $\{\varepsilon_{n,m}\}$ such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon_{n,m} = 0$ almost surely and*

$$\hat{\Theta}_{n,m} \subseteq \tilde{\Theta}_n(\varepsilon_{n,m}).$$

Remark 1.6.1 *Theorem 1.6.2 guarantees that with the appropriate assumptions, eventually, $\hat{\Theta}_{n,m}$ is almost surely contained in marginally inflated versions of the asymptotic confidence ellipsoid for the least squares estimate.*

1.7 Ellipsoidal Outer Approximation

The SPS confidence regions can become computationally demanding in the following sense: if a θ vector is given, checking whether θ is included in the confidence region is an easy task. The necessary steps include the calculation and the comparison of the $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|^2\}$ values. On the other hand, constructing the whole confidence region by testing every point is typically not feasible. A simple approximation method could be to check each parameter value on a sufficiently fine grid. However, even this approach is rather time-consuming and suffers from the ‘‘curse of dimensionality’’.

In this section, an approximation algorithm for the SPS method is presented, which can be computed efficiently (in polynomial time) and it offers ellipsoidal over-bounds.

By expanding $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$, it can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 &= \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^\top \theta) \right]^\top R_n^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^\top \theta) \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^\top (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \right]^\top R_n^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \varphi_k^\top (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \right] \\ &= (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n). \end{aligned}$$

The random ordering when $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$ and $\|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ are equal is ignored. The set, defined by the values of θ , where q of the $\|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ values are bigger or equal than $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$ is

$$\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq r(\theta) \right\},$$

where $r(\theta)$ is the q th largest value of the functions $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|^2\}$ for $i \in [m-1]$. The main idea is to replace $r(\theta)$ with an independent parameter r .

By comparing $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2$ with a single $\|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ function, it follows that

$$\{\theta : \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2\} \subseteq \{\theta : \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \max_{\theta: \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2} \|S_i(\theta)\|^2\}.$$

The inequality $\|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^T R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) &\leq \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta) \right]^T R_n^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k (y_k - \varphi_k^T \theta) \right] \\ &= \theta^T Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i \theta - 2\theta^T Q_i R_n^{-1} \psi_i + \psi_i^T R_n^{-1} \psi_i, \end{aligned}$$

where the matrix Q_i and the vector ψ_i are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} Q_i &\doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k \varphi_k^T, \\ \psi_i &\doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k} \varphi_k y_k, \end{aligned}$$

By noting that

$$\max_{\theta: \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2} \|S_i(\theta)\|^2 = \max_{\theta: \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2} \|S_0(\theta)\|^2$$

and by using the notation $z \doteq R_n^{1/2T}(\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)$, the value of $\max_{\theta: \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2} \|S_i(\theta)\|^2$ can be obtained by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{maximize} \quad \|z\|^2 \\ &\text{subject to} \quad z^T A_i z + 2z^T b_i + c_i \leq 0, \end{aligned} \tag{1.1}$$

where A_i, b_i, c_i are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_i &\doteq I - R_n^{-1/2} Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i R_n^{-1/2T}, \\ b_i &\doteq R_n^{-1/2} Q_i R_n^{-1} (\psi_i - Q_i \hat{\theta}_n), \\ c_i &\doteq -\psi_i^T R_n^{-1} \psi_i + 2\hat{\theta}_n^T Q_i R_n^{-1} \psi_i - \hat{\theta}_n^T Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i \hat{\theta}_n. \end{aligned}$$

The problem in (1.1) is generally not convex, however, strong duality holds. Therefore, the optimal value of (1.1) is equal to the solution of the dual problem, which is the following task:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{maximize} \quad \gamma \\ &\text{subject to} \quad \rho \geq 0 \\ &\quad \quad \quad \begin{bmatrix} -I + \lambda A_i & \lambda b_i \\ \lambda b_i^T & \lambda c_i + \gamma \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \end{aligned} \tag{1.2}$$

where $\succeq 0$ means that the matrix must be positive semidefinite. The problem described

in (1.2) is convex. By denoting its optimal solution by γ_i^* , it follows that

$$\{\theta : \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|^2\} \subseteq \{\theta : \|S_0(\theta)\|^2 \leq \gamma_i^*\}.$$

Therefore,

$$\hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq \hat{\hat{\Theta}}_n \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq r\},$$

where r is the q th largest value of γ_i^* , where $i \in [l-1]$. Since it is an outer-approximation, it follows that

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\hat{\Theta}}_n) \geq 1 - \frac{q}{l} = p$$

for any finite n . Algorithm 3 summarizes the construction.

Algorithm 3 SPS-Outer-Approximation

- 1: Compute the least squares estimate, namely

$$\hat{\theta}_n = R_n^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k y_k \right].$$

- 2: For $i \in [l-1]$, solve optimization problem (1.2) and let γ_i^* be the optimal solution.
- 3: Let r denote the q th largest γ_i^* value.
- 4: The outer approximation of the SPS confidence region is given by the ellipsoid

$$\hat{\hat{\Theta}}_n \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) \leq r\}.$$

Chapter 2

Fourier Analysis

Fourier Analysis plays a vital role in many fields, such as engineering [59, 60], biology [61, 62], signal processing [63, 64], physics [59, 65] and mathematics [66, 67]. The Fourier transform method is an integral transform of functions, which returns a function that describes the frequencies of the original function.

Since our goal is to construct guaranteed confidence bands for the regression function, we somehow have to restrict the set of functions, for which we aim to solve this task. If the possible values of the support of the Fourier transform for a function are within a given interval (or hypercube for the multivariate case), the boundaries of this interval essentially quantify how quickly the values of this function can change within small steps.

2.1 Fourier Transform and its Inverse

In this section, we will define the Fourier transform, then state the Fourier inversion theorem. We will also show, that the rectangular and the sinc functions are Fourier transform pairs [68]. This connection plays an important role on the space of functions that we are working on.

Definition 2.1.1 (Fourier transform) *Let $f(x)$ be a Lebesgue integrable function, where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The Fourier transform of f , denoted by $\hat{f}(t)$ is defined by the following integral:*

$$\hat{f}(t) \doteq \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(x) e^{-2\pi i t^\top x} dx.$$

Theorem 2.1.1 (Fourier inversion theorem) *Let $f(x)$ be a Lebesgue integrable function, where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. If $\hat{f}(t)$ is the Fourier transform of f , then*

$$f(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} e^{2\pi i t^\top x} \hat{f}(t) dt.$$

Remark 2.1.1 Functions $f(x)$ and $\hat{f}(t)$ are called a *Fourier pair* or *Fourier transform pairs*; and the function which maps $f(x)$ to $\hat{f}(t)$ from Theorem 2.1.1 is called the *inverse Fourier transform*.

Next, we will show that the rectangular and the sinc functions form a Fourier transform pair, as they will play an important role in the forthcoming theory of confidence bands. For simplicity, we will show this for the 1-dimensional case. First, let us define the rectangular function [68, Chapter 2].

$$\Pi(x) \doteq \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } |x| < 1/2 \\ 0, & |x| \geq 1/2 \end{cases}$$

Here, we used a definition, which didn't include scaling. There are also other conventions, in which the value of $\Pi(\pm 1/2)$ equals $1/2$ [69] or 1 [70], and in some cases, these values are not defined. Next, we define the sinc function

$$\text{sinc}(x) \doteq \begin{cases} \frac{\sin(x)}{x}, & \text{if } x \neq 0 \\ 1, & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

The Fourier transform is the following:

$$\hat{\Pi}(t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \Pi(x) e^{-2\pi i t x} dx = \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} 1 \cdot e^{-2\pi i t x} dx = \frac{\sin \pi t}{\pi t} = \text{sinc}(\pi t).$$

2.2 Basic Properties

In this section, we describe some of the basic properties of the Fourier transform [71].

Statement 2.2.1 Let $f, g \in \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$. Let $\hat{f}(t)$ and $\hat{g}(t)$ denote the Fourier transform of these functions, respectively. Then, the following properties are satisfied:

- **Continuity:** The function $t \rightarrow \hat{f}(t)$ is uniformly continuous.
- **Contraction:** The mapping $f \rightarrow \hat{f}$ is norm decreasing from \mathcal{L}^1 to \mathcal{L}^∞ in the sense that

$$|\hat{f}(t)| \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} |f(x)| dx = \|f\|_1.$$

- **Linearity:** $a\hat{f} + b\hat{g}$ is the Fourier transform of $a f + b g$ for $a, b \in \mathbb{C}$.
- **Translation and Phase Factor:** For $a \in \mathbb{R}$, the Fourier transform of $f(x - a)$ is $e^{-2\pi i a t} \hat{f}(t)$. For $b \in \mathbb{R}$, $\hat{f}(t + b)$ is the Fourier transform of $e^{-2\pi i b x} f(x)$.

- **Multiplication and Convolution:** $\hat{f}\hat{g}$ is the Fourier transform of $(f * g)$, where the convolution of these functions is defined as follows:

$$(f * g)(x) \doteq \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(y)g(x - y)dy.$$

- **Differentiation and Multiplication:** If $(\partial f / \partial x_j)$ exists and it is in $\mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$, then $2\pi i t_j \hat{f}(t)$ is the Fourier transform of $(\partial f / \partial x_j)$. If $x_j f \in \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$, then $(\partial \hat{f} / \partial t_j)(t)$ exists and is the Fourier transform of $-2\pi i x_j f(x)$.

2.3 Paley-Wiener Spaces

Paley-Wiener spaces play an important role in both Fourier analysis and sampling theory [27, 72]. They will also be crucial for our confidence band construction.

Definition 2.3.1 (Paley-Wiener Spaces) A Paley-Wiener space \mathcal{H} is a subspace of $\mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$, where for each $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$ the support of the Fourier transform of φ is included in a given hypercube $[-\eta, \eta]^d$, where $\eta > 0$ is a hyper-parameter.

Later, we will need that the Dirac evaluation operator $E_x : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $E_x(f) = f(x)$, is a bounded linear functional [27], for each $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. We will show this now. Let $f \in \mathcal{H}$. Then, there exists a function $\hat{f} \in \mathcal{L}^2[-\eta, \eta]^d$ such that

$$f(x) = \int_{[-\eta, \eta]^d} \hat{f}(t) e^{2\pi i x^T t} dt.$$

Let us denote the inverse Fourier transformation with ℓ . It holds that the linear map

$$\ell : \mathcal{L}^2[-\eta, \eta]^d \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$$

is one-to-one. In order to prove this, we can use that the functions $(e^{2\pi i n t / \eta})^d$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ form an orthonormal basis for $\mathcal{L}^2[-\eta, \eta]^d$. Hence, $\ell(\hat{f})(n/\eta) = f(n/\eta) = 0$ for each $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ implies $\hat{f} = 0$. The map ℓ is linear, one-to-one and onto. By defining a norm on \mathcal{H} as

$$\|\ell(f)\| = \|f\|_2,$$

then \mathcal{H} is a Hilbert space and ℓ is a Hilbert space isomorphism. Then, for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, E_x is a bounded linear operator, since for any $f \in \mathcal{H}$, we have

$$|E_x(f)| = |f(x)| = \left| \int_{[-\eta, \eta]^d} \hat{f}(t) e^{2\pi i x^T t} dt \right| \leq \|\hat{f}\|_2 \|e^{2\pi i x^T t}\|_2 = \sqrt{2\eta} \|f\|.$$

Chapter 3

Kernels in Machine Learning

Kernel methods are based on the concept of Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces (RKHSs) and they have a wide range of applications in statistics and machine learning [28]. One of the main reasons of their popularity is the representer theorem, which states that an estimation in any infinite dimensional space of functions forming an RKHS can be solved in a finite dimensional space. Kernel methods are fundamental tools of nonparametric statistics, and they are especially useful for providing distribution-free inference, even though their special cases include Gaussian process regression. In this section, the main theoretical background of RKHSs is summarized. Together with the characterization of reproducing kernels, the interpolation problem with properties of the unique solution in RKHSs is also stated. The description mostly follows the book of [27].

Since Paley-Wiener spaces are RKHSs on \mathbb{R}^d , we will be able to use the RKHS theory in the construction of our method. A key function in our algorithms is the minimum norm interpolant, which interpolates each output of a sample at the corresponding input and it is the smoothest among such functions in the space (measured by the RKHS norm). The core idea of our method will come from calculating the minimum norm needed to interpolate the original dataset extended by any query input-output pair.

3.1 Reproducing Kernels

Let $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{R})$ denote the set of functions from the (nonempty) set \mathbb{X} to \mathbb{R} . Then, the set $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{R})$ will be a vector space over \mathbb{R} with respect to addition, $(f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x)$ and scalar multiplication $(\lambda \cdot f)(x) = \lambda \cdot (f(x))$.

Definition 3.1.1 (Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space) *Let \mathbb{X} be a nonempty set. A subset $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{R})$ is called a reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS) on \mathbb{X} if*

1. \mathcal{H} is a vector subspace of $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{R})$;

2. \mathcal{H} is endowed with an inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ with respect to \mathcal{H} which is a Hilbert space,
3. for every $x \in \mathbb{X}$, the linear evaluation functional $E_x : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is defined by $E_x(f) = f(x)$ is bounded.

By using the Riesz representation theorem, a specific kernel can be constructed: for each $x \in \mathbb{X}$, a unique $k_x \in \mathcal{H}$ vector exists such that $f(x) = E_x(f) = \langle f, k_x \rangle$ for each $f \in \mathcal{H}$.

Definition 3.1.2 (Reproducing kernel) *The Riesz representation k_x of the linear evaluation functional is called the kernel for point x . The bivariate function $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $k(x, y) = k_y(x)$ is called the reproducing kernel of \mathcal{H} .*

The kernel of an RKHS is a symmetric and a positive-definite function, and the Moore-Aronszajn theorem states, that the converse also holds true: for every symmetric and positive-definite function, there exists a unique RKHS [28].

Definition 3.1.3 *A function $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called a positive type function, or a positive definite function, if we have*

$$\forall n \geq 1, \forall (a_1, \dots, a_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n, \forall (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{X}^n, \\ \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n a_i a_j k(x_i, x_j) \in \mathbb{R}_0^+,$$

where \mathbb{R}_0^+ denotes the set of nonnegative real numbers.

Theorem 3.1.1 (Moore-Aronszajn) *Let k be a real-valued, symmetric, positive type function on $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X}$. Then, there exists exactly one reproducing kernel Hilbert space \mathcal{H} of real-valued functions on \mathbb{X} with k as its reproducing kernel.*

3.2 Characterization of Reproducing Kernels

In this section, we focus on certain statements, which provide necessary and sufficient conditions for a function to be the reproducing kernel for some RKHS.

Definition 3.2.1 (Gram matrix of a kernel) *The Gram matrix of kernel k with respect to the input points $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{X}$ is $K_{i,j} \doteq k(x_i, x_j)$ for all $i, j \in [n]$.*

Observation 3.2.1 *Let \mathbb{X} be a nonempty set and let $K : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a reproducing kernel, i.e., a symmetric and positive definite function. Then, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and every choice of n points $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$, Gram matrix $K_{i,j} = k(x_i, x_j)$ is positive semidefinite.*

Statement 3.2.1 *Let \mathbb{X} be a set and \mathcal{H} be an RKHS on \mathbb{X} with reproducing kernel k . Then k is kernel function.*

The conversion of this statement also holds true, and it provides the characterization of reproducing kernel functions, see Theorem 3.1.1.

Definition 3.2.2 *A kernel will be called strictly positive definite, if its Gram matrix is positive definite for all distinct $\{x_k\} \in \mathbb{X}$ inputs, $k \in [n]$, for all sample size n .*

The representer theorem is a core result, which states that the minimizer of a loss or penalty function over an RKHS can be represented from a finite linear combination by the values of the kernel function for the data observations [27, Theorem 8.7].

Theorem 3.2.1 *Let \mathcal{H} be an RKHS on \mathbb{X} , let $W : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a monotonically increasing function, and let $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n \subseteq \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{R}$ be a sample. Consider the cost function $J(f) = W(\|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2) + L(f(x_1), \dots, f(x_n), y_1, \dots, y_n) \in \mathbb{R}$. If $f^* \in \mathcal{H}$ is a function such that $J(f^*) = \inf_{f \in \mathcal{H}} J(f)$, then f^* is in the span of the functions k_{x_1}, \dots, k_{x_n} , that is, it takes the form*

$$f^*(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(x, x_i),$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, where $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n \in \mathbb{R}$. Note that function L can be arbitrary.

3.3 Typical Kernels

In this section, we will provide some examples for typical kernels and RKHSs.

Example 3.3.1 (Gaussian kernel) *For $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and $f \in \mathcal{H}$, the Gaussian kernel is defined as*

$$k(x, y) = \exp(-\|x - y\|^2 / 2\sigma^2),$$

where $\sigma > 0$.

Example 3.3.2 (Polynomial kernel) *For $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and $f \in \mathcal{H}$, the Polynomial kernel is defined as*

$$k(x, y) = (\langle x, y \rangle + c)^p,$$

where $c \geq 0$ and $p \in \mathbb{N}$.

Example 3.3.3 (Sigmoidal kernel) *For $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and $f \in \mathcal{H}$, the Sigmoidal kernel is the following:*

$$k(x, y) = \tanh(a\langle x, y \rangle + b),$$

for some $a, b \geq 0$ (note: not all a, b choices lead to kernels).

3.4 Basic Examples for RKHSs

Let $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n), y = (y_1, \dots, y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and let

$$\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{k=1}^n x_k y_k.$$

The reproducing kernel of \mathbb{R}^n is the following:

$$k(x_i, x_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j \\ 0, & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}.$$

Also, generally, for any discrete set \mathbb{X} , let us introduce

$$\mathfrak{L}_2(X) \doteq \left\{ f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \sum_{x \in \mathbb{X}} |f(x)|^2 < \infty \right\}.$$

For arbitrary $x, y \in \mathfrak{L}_2(\mathbb{X})$, let

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{X}} f(x)g(x),$$

With the above definitions, $\mathfrak{L}_2(\mathbb{X})$ is a Hilbert space of functions on \mathbb{X} . Let $y \in \mathbb{X}$ be fixed. By defining $e_y \in \mathfrak{L}_2(\mathbb{X})$ denote the following function:

$$e_y(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = y \\ 0, & \text{if } x \neq y \end{cases}.$$

Since $\{e_y\}_{y \in \mathbb{X}}$ is an orthonormal basis in $\mathfrak{L}_2(\mathbb{X})$ and $\langle f, e_y \rangle = f(y)$, these functions are the reproducing kernels and

$$k(x, y) = \langle e_y, e_x \rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = y \\ 0, & \text{if } x \neq y \end{cases}.$$

3.5 Sobolev Spaces on $[0, 1]$

Before providing this example, we define the absolutely continuous functions.

Definition 3.5.1 *A function $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is absolutely continuous if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$, so that when $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ are non-overlapping intervals from $[0, 1]$ with $\sum_{j=1}^n |y_j - x_j| < \delta$, then $\sum_{j=1}^n |f(y_j) - f(x_j)| < \varepsilon$.*

Remark 3.5.1 *Absolutely continuous functions are equivalent to the functions, which satisfy the first fundamental theorem of calculus.*

We denote the set of $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ absolutely continuous functions, for which f' is square-integrable and $f(0) = f(1) = 0$ holds with \mathcal{H} .

Observation 3.5.1 \mathcal{H} is a vector space on $[0, 1]$.

To make \mathcal{H} a Hilbert space, the following nonnegative form is introduced:

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \int_0^1 f'(t)g(t) dt.$$

Since \mathcal{H} is also complete in the norm, which is given by its inner product, this space is a reproducing kernel Hilbert space [27].

3.6 Hardy Space of the Unit Disk

The Hardy space plays an important role in many fields, such as function theory and operator theory. By introducing the complex series f as

$$f \sim \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k z^k,$$

such that $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} |a_k|^2 < \infty$, an inner product can be defined with another series g with this property as follows:

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k \bar{b}_k.$$

From this, it follows, that $\|f\|^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} |a_k|^2$. The associated space is an RKHS and its reproducing kernel is called the *Szegő kernel*:

$$k(x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \bar{y}^k x^k = \frac{1}{1 - \bar{y}x}.$$

3.7 Paley-Wiener Spaces

In Section 2.3, we have already defined the Paley-Wiener spaces. We have also proven, that the Dirac evaluation operator, E_x , is bounded for each x , thus, Paley-Wiener spaces are *Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces* (RKHSs). Their reproducing kernel is as follows:

$$k(u, v) \doteq \pi^{-d} \prod_{j=1}^m \frac{\sin(\eta(u_j - v_j))}{u_j - v_j},$$

where $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and, for convenience, $\sin(\eta \cdot 0)/0$ is defined to be η . It is important to note that the above defined reproducing kernel k is a strictly positive definite. Recall that a Paley-Wiener space contains *band-limited* functions.

3.8 Interpolation

In our construction, the primary application of the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces will be to interpolation problems. In this section, we give a brief description of the problem and we also discuss some of the theoretical results.

Definition 3.8.1 *Let \mathbb{X} and \mathbb{Y} be sets and let $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ be a collection of distinct points, and let $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{Y}$ be subsets. A function $g : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{Y}$ interpolates these points if $g(x_i) = \lambda_i$ for all $i \in [n]$.*

Let $\mathcal{H}_F \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ denote the subspace spanned by the kernel functions $\{k_{x_1}, \dots, k_{x_n}\}$ given a finite set $F = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ of distinct points and P_F will denote the orthogonal projection of \mathcal{H} onto \mathcal{H}_F .

Observation 3.8.1 *For any $h \in \mathcal{H}$, it holds that*

$$P_F(h)(x_i) = h(x_i), \quad \text{for } i \in [n].$$

Statement 3.8.1 *Let $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ be a set of distinct points from \mathbb{X} and let $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$. If there exists $g \in \mathcal{H}$ that interpolates these values, then $P_F(g)$ is the unique function of minimum norm that interpolates these values.*

Interpolation in an RKHS is possible with a uniquely constructed function, guaranteed by the following theorem [27].

Theorem 3.8.1 *Let \mathcal{H} be an RKHS on the set \mathbb{X} with reproducing kernel k . Let $F = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ be distinct points and let $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$. Then there exists $g \in \mathcal{H}$ that interpolates these values if and only if $v = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n)^T$ is in the range of the Gram matrix $K(x_i, x_j)$. Moreover, in this case if we choose $w = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)^T$ to be any vector whose image is v , then $h = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k_{x_i}$ is the unique function of minimal norm in \mathcal{H} that interpolates these points. Moreover, $\|h\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \langle v, w \rangle$.*

Remark 3.8.1 *By using the reproducing property, this implies*

$$\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \hat{\alpha}^T K \hat{\alpha}.$$

Next, a theorem is stated with equivalent definitions for strictly definite kernel functions, which shows that this property is closely tied to interpolation [27, Theorem 3.6].

Theorem 3.8.2 *Let \mathbb{X} be a set and let $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a kernel. Then the following are equivalent:*

1. k is strictly positive,

2. for any n and any set of distinct points $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, the kernel functions k_{x_1}, \dots, k_{x_n} are linearly independent,

3. for any n and any set of distinct points $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, and any set $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ that are not all 0, there exists $f \in \mathcal{H}(k)$ with

$$\alpha_1 f(x_1) + \dots + \alpha_n f(x_n) \neq 0,$$

4. for any n and any set of distinct points $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, there exist functions $g_1, \dots, g_n \in \mathcal{H}(k)$, satisfying

$$g_i(x_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j \\ 0, & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}$$

Definition 3.8.2 An RKHS \mathcal{H} on \mathbb{X} , which satisfies any of the equivalent condition on Theorem 3.8.2 is called fully interpolating.

3.9 Kernel Ridge Regression

The Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR) is the kernelized version of the regularized Least Squares problem [45]. The optimization problem can be written in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize} \quad & \lambda \|w\|^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_k^2 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & y_k - \langle w \cdot x_k \rangle = \xi_k, \quad k \in [n] \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where $\lambda > 0$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the weight vector. From (3.1), the Lagrangian is:

$$\text{minimize} \quad L(w, \xi, \mu) = \lambda \|w\|^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_k^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k (y_k - \langle w \cdot x_k \rangle - \xi_k). \tag{3.2}$$

By taking the gradient of (3.2) with respect to w and μ and imposing stationarity, we obtain the following equations:

$$w = \frac{1}{2\lambda} \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k x_k \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_k = \mu_k / 2.$$

By using these results, the following dual problem follows:

$$\text{maximize} \quad W(\mu) = \sum_{k=1}^n y_k \mu_k - \frac{1}{4\lambda} \sum_{k,l=1}^n \mu_k \mu_l \langle x_k \cdot x_l \rangle - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k^2. \tag{3.3}$$

Rewriting the term in (3.3) vector form yields

$$W(\mu) = y^T \mu - \frac{1}{4\lambda} \mu^T K \mu - \frac{1}{4} \mu^T \mu. \quad (3.4)$$

By taking the gradient of (3.4) with respect to μ and imposing stationarity, it follows that

$$-\frac{1}{2\lambda} K \mu - \frac{1}{2} \mu + y = 0,$$

which yields

$$\mu = 2\lambda(K + \lambda I_n)^{-1} y$$

with the corresponding regression function

$$f_*(x) = \langle w \cdot x \rangle = y^T (K + \lambda I_n)^{-1} k,$$

where k denotes the vector with entries $k_k = \langle x_k \cdot x \rangle$ for $k \in [n]$. From this, the next statement follows.

Statement 3.9.1 *Given data sample $((x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n))$ we want to perform regression using the feature space implicitly defined by the kernel k . Let $f_*(x) = y^T (K + \lambda I_n)^{-1} k$, where $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the Gram matrix and k denotes the vector with entries $k_k = \langle x_k \cdot x \rangle$ for $k \in [n]$. Then $f_*(x)$ is equivalent to the hyperplane in the feature space implicitly defined by the kernel k that solves the ridge regression problem defined in (3.1).*

Next, we will show that the KRR task can be formulated as a canonical least squares problem following [73]. This formulation will be used later to provide confidence bands for the regression function.

The (weighted) KRR estimation is given in the following form:

$$\hat{f}_{\text{KRR}} \in \arg \min_{\mathcal{H}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n w_k (y_k - f_*(x_k))^2 + \lambda \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

where $\lambda > 0, w_k > 0, k \in [n]$ are a priori given constant weights. By denoting the data set by $\mathcal{D}_n \doteq \{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$ and using the Representer theorem, the objective function can be rewritten as in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} g(f_\alpha, \mathcal{D}_n) &\doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n w_k (y_k - f_\alpha(x_k))^2 + \lambda \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \|y - f_\alpha(x)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \lambda (\|f_*\|) \\ &= \frac{1}{n} (y - K\alpha)^T W (y - K\alpha) + \lambda \alpha^T K \alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

where $f_\alpha(x) \doteq [f_\alpha(x_1), \dots, f_\alpha(x_n)]^T$, $W \doteq \text{diag}(w_1, \dots, w_n)$ and $\alpha \doteq [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n]^T$.

Next, the equation (3.5) can be written in a canonical form $\|z - \Phi\alpha\|^2$ by using the following variables:

$$\Phi \doteq \begin{pmatrix} (1/\sqrt{n}) W^{1/2} K \\ \sqrt{\lambda} K^{1/2} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad z \doteq \begin{pmatrix} (1/\sqrt{n}) W^{1/2} y \\ 0_n \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.6)$$

where $W^{1/2}$ and $K^{1/2}$ denote the square roots of matrices W and K .

Observation 3.9.1 *Since the matrices W and K are always positive semidefinite, their square root always exists.*

Chapter 4

Gaussian Process Regression

In this section, we give a brief overview of a special kernel method, with a slightly more restrictive practical applicability. If the data is jointly Gaussian, a powerful construction is offered by Gaussian process regression, which, besides point estimates, is also able to provide (guaranteed) prediction regions for the outputs, and credible regions for the expected outputs. The description is based on the book [40].

4.1 Bayesian Linear Regression

First, we give a short overview of the Bayesian analysis of the standard linear regression model. The problem comes in the following form:

$$f_*(x) = x^T \theta, \quad y = f_*(x) + \varepsilon,$$

where x is the input vector, θ is the vector of weights of the linear model, f_* is the function value, y is the observed target value and ε is the measurement noise, which is assumed to follow an independent, identically distributed Gaussian distribution:

$$\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_n^2).$$

This assumption with the model directly provides the following.

$$\begin{aligned} p(y|X, \theta) &= \prod_{i=1}^n p(y_i|x_i, \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_n} \exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - x_i^T \theta)^2}{2\sigma_n^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma_n^2)^{n/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma_n^2}|y - X^T \theta|^2\right) = \mathcal{N}(X^T \theta, \sigma_n^2 I), \end{aligned}$$

where p is the probability density, X denotes the $d \times n$ *design matrix*, which contains the column vectors of the inputs and $|z|$ means the Euclidean length of vector z .

In the Bayesian formalism, one needs to specify a *prior* over the parameters, which

essentially decodes the beliefs about the parameters before looking at the observations. A zero mean Gaussian prior is put on the weights with covariance matrix $\Sigma_p \succ 0$:

$$\theta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_p).$$

By using Bayes' rule, the inference in the Bayesian linear model is computed as follows:

$$p(\theta|y, X) = \frac{p(y|X, \theta)p(\theta)}{p(y|X)},$$

where the normalizing constant is independent of the weights and given by

$$p(y|X) = \int p(y|X, \theta)p(\theta) d\theta.$$

Also, by only writing out the terms from the likelihood and prior which depend on the weights, we have

$$\begin{aligned} p(\theta|X, y) &\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma_n^2}(y - X^T\theta)^T(y - X^T\theta)\right) \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\theta^T\Sigma_p^{-1}\theta\right) \\ &\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\theta - \bar{\theta})^T\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_n^2}XX^T + \Sigma_p^{-1}\right)(\theta - \bar{\theta})\right), \end{aligned}$$

where \propto denotes proportional to and $\bar{\theta} = \sigma_n^{-2}(\sigma_n^{-2}XX^T + \Sigma_p^{-1})^{-1}Xy$. By denoting $A = \sigma_n^{-2}XX^T + \Sigma_p^{-1}$, we have

$$p(\theta|X, y) \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{\theta} = \frac{1}{\sigma_n^2}A^{-1}Xy, A^{-1}).$$

In order to make predictions for a test case, one has to average over all possible parameter values, weighted by their posterior probability. The predictive distribution for $f_*(x_*)$ is given by the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} p(f_*(x_*)|x_*, X, y) &= \int p(f_*(x_*)|x_*, \theta) p(\theta|X, y) d\theta = \int x_*^T\theta p(\theta|X, y) d\theta \\ &\stackrel{d}{=} \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2}x_*^T A^{-1}Xy, x_*^T A^{-1}x_*\right). \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Formal Description

We start by defining a Gaussian process (GP) for describing a distribution over functions.

Definition 4.2.1 *A Gaussian process is a collection of random variables, any finite number of which have a joint Gaussian distribution.*

A Gaussian process is completely defined by its mean function and covariance function. For the real process $\{y_k\}$, the mean function f_* and the covariance function k is defined as follows: for $p, q \in [n]$:

$$f_*(x_p) = \mathbb{E}[y_p],$$

$$k(x_p, x_q) = \mathbb{E}[(y_p - f_*(x_p))(y_q - f_*(x_q))],$$

and the Gaussian process is written as

$$y \sim \mathcal{GP}(f_*, k).$$

Remark 4.2.1 *Since a Gaussian process is defined as a collection of random variables, this definition implies a consistency requirement: this property means that if the GP specifies $(y_1, y_2) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$, then it must also specify $y_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, \Sigma_{11})$, where Σ_{11} is the corresponding submatrix of Σ .*

This requirement means, that examination of a larger set of variables does not change the distribution of the smaller set. For example, this consistency requirement is automatically fulfilled if the covariance function specifies the entries of a covariance matrix.

For an example of a Gaussian process, in this section, we will take the Bayesian linear regression model, namely $f_*(x) = x^T \theta$ with prior $\theta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_p)$. For the mean and covariance, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[y(x)] = \mathbb{E}[x^T \theta] = x^T \mathbb{E}[\theta] = 0,$$

$$\mathbb{E}[y(x)y(x')] = x \mathbb{E}[\theta \theta^T] x' = x^T \Sigma_p x'.$$

Hence, both $y(x)$ and $y(x')$ are jointly Gaussian with zero mean and covariance $x^T \Sigma_p x'$.

In this section, we take the following example for the covariance function:

$$\text{cov}(y(x_p), y(x_q)) = k(x_p, x_q) = \exp(-1/2 \cdot |x_p - x_q|^2). \quad (4.1)$$

This covariance function is called the squared exponential (SE) covariance function.

Let us draw samples from the distribution of functions evaluated at any number of points. Namely, we choose a number of input points, denoted by X_* and we write out the corresponding covariance matrix elementwise using (4.1). This generates a random Gaussian vector with the following covariance matrix:

$$y_* \sim \mathcal{N}(0, K(X_*, X_*)).$$

4.3 Prediction with Noise-Free Outputs

In this section, we consider the case where the outputs are noise-free, namely we have knowledge about $\{(x_i, f_*(x_i)), i \in [n]\}$. The outputs are divided into training and test outputs: the joint distribution of the training outputs y , the joint distribution of the test outputs y_* according to the prior is the following:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y \\ y_* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \begin{bmatrix} K(X, X) & K(X, X_*) \\ K(X_*, X) & K(X_*, X_*) \end{bmatrix}\right).$$

Figure 4.1: GPR: Noise-Free Observations.

Let us denote the number of the training outputs by n and the number of the test outputs by n_* . Then, $K(X, X_*)$ denotes the matrix with dimensions n and n_* , where the elements are the covariances evaluated at all pairs of training and test points, similarly for the remaining matrices.

To get the posterior distribution over functions we need to restrict this joint prior distribution to contain only those functions which agree with the observed data points. One can also think of this as generating functions from the prior, and rejecting the ones which disagree with the observations.

By conditioning the joint Gaussian prior distribution on the observations, we have

$$y_* | X_*, X, y \sim \mathcal{N}(K(X_*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}y, K(X_*, X_*) - K(X_*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}K(X, X_*)). \quad (4.2)$$

Function values y_* can be sampled from the joint posterior distribution by evaluating the mean and covariance matrix from (4.1).

Figure 4.1 demonstrates the method for the noise-free case. Both the mean prediction and confidence intervals are plotted.

4.4 Prediction with Noisy Observations

In order to achieve realistic results, one has to work with the case where we no longer have access to perfect function values, but only noisy versions of $y = f(x) + \varepsilon$, where

the noise is assumed to be an additive, independent and identically distributed Gaussian with variance σ_n^2 . The prior on the noisy observations becomes:

$$\text{cov}(y_p, y_q) = k(x_p, x_q) + \sigma_n^2 \delta_{pq} \quad \text{or} \quad \text{cov}(y_p, y_q) = K(X, X) + \sigma_n^2 I,$$

where δ_{pq} denotes the Kronecker delta, which takes value 1 iff $p = q$ and zero otherwise. The joint distribution of the observed target values and the function values at the test locations under the prior can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} y \\ y_* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \begin{bmatrix} K(X, X) + \sigma_n^2 I & K(X, X_*) \\ K(X_*, X) & K(X_*, X_*) \end{bmatrix}\right).$$

For the Gaussian process regression, by using (4.2), we obtain the following equations:

$$y_* | X, y, X_* \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{y}_*, \text{cov}(y_*)), \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$\bar{y}_* \doteq \mathbb{E}[y_* | X, y, X_*] = K(X_*, X)[K(X, X) + \sigma_n^2 I]^{-1} y, \quad (4.4)$$

$$\text{cov}(y_*) = K(X, X_*) - K(X_*, X)[K(X, X) + \sigma_n^2 I]^{-1} K(X, X_*). \quad (4.5)$$

By introducing the notations $K \doteq K(X, X)$, $K_* \doteq K(X, X_*)$, $k(x_*) = k_*$, equations (4.4) and (4.5) can be rewritten as

$$\bar{y}_* = k_*^\top (K + \sigma_n^2 I)^{-1} y, \quad (4.6)$$

$$\mathbb{V}[f_*] = k(x_*, x_*) - k_*^\top (K + \sigma_n^2 I)^{-1} k_*. \quad (4.7)$$

Remark 4.4.1 *The mean prediction (4.6) is a linear combination of observations y .*

This equation can also be seen as a linear combination of n kernel functions, each one centered on a training point, namely

$$\bar{y}(x_*) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(x_i, x_*), \quad (4.8)$$

where $\alpha = (K + \sigma_n^2 I)^{-1} y$.

The representation obtained by (4.8) is due to the representer theorem.

Remark 4.4.2 *The variance in (4.7) does not depend on the observed targets, but only on the inputs, thanks to the Gaussian distribution.*

Figure 4.2 demonstrates the method for the noisy case. Both the mean prediction and confidence intervals are plotted.

Figure 4.2: GPR: Noisy Observations.

4.5 Connection to Kernel Ridge Regression

For the case of regularization, we consider the following functional:

$$J[f] = \frac{\lambda}{2} \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + Q(y, f), \quad (4.9)$$

where y is the vector of the predicted targets, $f = (f(x_1), \dots, f(x_n))^T$ is the corresponding vector of function values and λ is a scaling parameter. The first term of (4.9) is called the *regularizer* and it encodes the smoothness of the function f by a suitable RKHS. The second term of (4.9) is a data-fit term, which measures the quality of the prediction. Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR) can be seen as a particular case of regularization. The representer theorem shows that each minimizer $f \in \mathcal{H}$ from $J[f]$ takes on the form $f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(x, x_i)$.

For Gaussian process prediction, the analogue of the representer theorem comes from the following fact: the distribution of $f(x_*)$ given the data y is

$$p(f(x_*)|f) = \int p(f(x_*)|f)p(f|y) \, df.$$

Due to the formula for the conditional distribution of a multivariate Gaussian, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[f(x_*)|y] = k(x_*)^T K^{-1} \mathbb{E}[f|y].$$

Therefore, we have $\mathbb{E}[f(x_*)|y] = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(x, x_i)$, where $\alpha = K^{-1} \mathbb{E}[f|y]$.

Part II

Scientific Contributions

Chapter 5

Overview

In this chapter, we present the core problem we study, our main assumptions and objectives. Next to that, by using the SPS method, we show an algorithm for constructing confidence bands for the case of finite dimensional model classes, then we provide a method to build confidence intervals at (observed) sample inputs in the nonparametric case. Finally, we give an overview of our general confidence band construction for (band-limited) regression functions and we summarize our main theoretical results.

5.1 Data Generation

Let us have $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$, a finite sample of i.i.d. input-output data pairs with an unknown $\mathbb{P}_{X,Y}$ joint distribution, where $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is an input vector and $y_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is a scalar output with $\mathbb{E}[y_k^2] < \infty$. We assume that

$$y_k = f_*(x_k) + \varepsilon_k,$$

for $k \in [n] \doteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, where $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ represent the (observation or measurement) noise terms on the “true” regression function f_* with $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_k] = 0$.

5.2 Objectives

Our primary goal is to construct confidence bands for the unknown f_* data-generating function, that have guaranteed (user-chosen) probabilities for finite, and possibly small number of data points. The goal of the obtained regions is to be *distribution-free*, which means that we do not have any distributional assumption for the noise terms affecting the data. Formally, our aim is to construct a function $I : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$, such that $I(x) = (I_1(x), I_2(x))$ specifies the endpoints of the interval estimate for the unknown $f_*(x)$ value, where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

Remark 5.2.1 *The band I also depends on the data, hence, it is a random object. Therefore, the formal definition of the function can also be written as $I : \mathbb{R}^d \times (\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R})^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$ and $I(x) = I(x, \{x_k, y_k\}_{k=1}^n)$ to emphasize the dependence on the observed data.*

For an $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ user-chosen probability (risk), let

$$\nu(I) \doteq \mathbb{P}(\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^d : I_1(x) \leq f_*(x) \leq I_2(x)) \geq 1 - \alpha. \quad (5.1)$$

$\nu(I)$ is called the *reliability* of the confidence band. Since the $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ part is inside the probability in (5.1), our confidence bands should also be *simultaneous*.

By introducing

$$\mathcal{I} \doteq \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R} : y \in [I_1(x), I_2(x)]\},$$

the reliability can be written as $\nu(I) = \mathbb{P}(\text{graph}(f_*) \subseteq \mathcal{I})$, where $\text{graph}(f_*) \doteq \{(x, f_*(x)) : x \in \mathbb{R}^d\}$. In the case of an empty interval, we will use the notion of $\mathcal{I}(x) = \emptyset$. Next to the reliability, we also want our confidence bands to shrink as the sample size increases, which concept is called consistency. Let

$$\mathcal{C} \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : \text{graph}(f) \subseteq \mathcal{I}\},$$

i.e., the set of those functions from \mathcal{H} that take their values inside the confidence band \mathcal{I} . We can also write \mathcal{C}_n , if we want to emphasize its dependence on the sample size n .

Definition 5.2.1 *We say that a (random) sequence of confidence sets $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$ is uniformly strongly consistent, if*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{n=k}^{\infty} \{\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq \mathcal{B}(f_*, \varepsilon)\} \right) = 1,$$

for all $\varepsilon > 0$, where $\mathcal{B}(f_*, \varepsilon) \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : \|f_* - f\|_{\mathcal{H}} \leq \varepsilon\}$.

Intuitively, strong consistency means that the functions compatible with the constructed confidence bands will eventually get arbitrarily close to the “true” regression function f_* .

5.3 Main Assumptions

Before stating our main assumptions, we first define distributional invariance, which needs to be fulfilled by the noise terms.

Definition 5.3.1 *A vector from \mathbb{R}^d is distributionally invariant with respect to a compact group of transformations, (\mathcal{G}, \circ) , where “ \circ ” denotes the function composition and each $G \in \mathcal{G}$ maps \mathbb{R}^d to itself, if for all $G \in \mathcal{G}$, vectors ε and $G(\varepsilon)$ have the same distribution.*

Observation 5.3.1 *Since the i.i.d. assumption is a special case of exchangeability, the distributional invariance property is automatically satisfied under A1: we can always work with the (finite) group of permutation matrices, as they leave the joint distribution of the noises unchanged. This is our default choice. On the other hand, if more information is available, we can refine the transformation group to obtain tighter bands.*

Our main assumptions on the data and the noise are the following:

A1 The dataset $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$ is an i.i.d. sample of inputs and outputs; and for all k : $\mathbb{E}[y_k^2] < \infty$.

A2 The probability distribution behind the inputs, $\{x_k\}$, is absolutely continuous, and its density function, h_* , has support \mathbb{R}^d , that is for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, we have $h_*(x) > 0$.

A3 The noises have zero mean, $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_k] = 0$, variables $\{x_k\}$ and $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ are independent, and $\varepsilon \doteq (\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n)^T$ is distributionally invariant w.r.t. a compact matrix group \mathcal{G} .

A4 Function f_* is from a Paley-Wiener space and there is a (universal) constant $\rho > 0$ with $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^d : f_*^2(x) \leq \rho h_*(x)$.

The i.i.d. requirement from A1 is a standard assumption in supervised learning. The assumption on the full support of the input distribution, A2, is needed to get information about the whole function. The A3 criterion on the measurement noise is rather mild. Two typical examples having this property are the following: if $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ are exchangeable, then we can use the finite group of permutations on the noise vector. If $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ are independent and symmetric, then we can use the group, which consists of sign-changes for any given subsets of the noise terms. The last assumption, A4 is required in order to restrict the model class and to ensure that we can generalize our results to unknown (out-of-sample) data points. This assumption also ensures, that we obtain most of our input observations near the peak of the original density function. The (universal) constant ρ in A4 measures how “informative” querying f_* at a random input is, a smaller value of ρ ensures that we get our observations from the more “interesting” part of f_* .

5.4 Confidence Bands for Finite Dimensional Models

In this section, we provide a basic idea to create simultaneous confidence bands for finite dimensional models by using the regions provided by Algorithm 3 (SPS Ellipsoidal Outer Approximation). We solve this by maximizing (and minimizing) a linear function over an ellipsoid: the solutions of these problems will provide the upper and the lower parts of

the confidence bands. We now prove that the solution of a linear objective function over an ellipsoid is always attained at the boundary of the ellipsoid.

The linear objective function with an ellipsoidal constraint take on the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \min / \max \quad & a^T x \\ \text{subject to} \quad & (x - \bar{x})^T P^{-1} (x - \bar{x}) \leq 1, \end{aligned} \tag{5.2}$$

where $a, x, \bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. The lemma below recalls a known result for the problem of maximizing or minimizing a linear function on an ellipsoidal domain.

Lemma 5.4.1 *The problems in (5.2) yield the following solutions:*

$$\begin{aligned} x_{max} &\doteq \bar{x} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^T P a}} P a, \\ x_{min} &\doteq \bar{x} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^T P a}} P a. \end{aligned}$$

Proof Since the objective function is piecewise affine, the maximum (and the minimum) are both attained at the boundary of the ellipsoid. Hence, let us consider the problem

$$\begin{aligned} \text{maximize} \quad & a^T x \\ \text{subject to} \quad & (x - \bar{x})^T P^{-1} (x - \bar{x}) = 1, \end{aligned}$$

We define the Lagrangian as follows:

$$L(x, \mu) = a^T x - \frac{\mu}{2} ((x - \bar{x})^T P^{-1} (x - \bar{x}) - 1). \tag{5.3}$$

By taking the gradient of (5.3) with respect to x and the derivative with respect to μ , we obtain the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} a - \mu P^{-1} (x - \bar{x}) &= 0 \\ (x - \bar{x})^T P^{-1} (x - \bar{x}) &= 1 \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

By multiplying (5.4) with P and re-arranging, we obtain:

$$\mu(x - \bar{x}) = P a$$

If $P a \neq 0$, then $\mu \neq 0$, therefore:

$$x - \bar{x} = \frac{1}{\mu} P a.$$

Using the equation of the ellipsoid, we obtain:

$$\mu^2 = a^T P^T P^{-1} P a = a^T P a,$$

where $a^T P a \geq 0$ because P is positive definite. Hence,

$$x - \bar{x} = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^T P a}} P a$$

and thus, the solutions of (5.2) are

$$\begin{aligned} x_{max} &\doteq \bar{x} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^T P a}} P a, \\ x_{min} &\doteq \bar{x} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^T P a}} P a. \end{aligned}$$

□

This lemma provides us with the construction of our confidence intervals for the linear regression model which then leads to simultaneous confidence bands.

Theorem 5.4.2 *Assuming S1 and S2, the intervals defined by*

$$I(\varphi) \doteq \left[\varphi^T \hat{\theta}_n - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varphi^T P \varphi}} P \varphi, \varphi^T \hat{\theta}_n + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varphi^T P \varphi}} P \varphi \right],$$

where $\varphi \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $P \doteq (1/r)R_n$ guarantee

$$\mathbb{P}(\forall \varphi \in \mathbb{R}^d : \varphi^T \theta^* \in I(\varphi)) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

where α is the user-chosen probability and θ^* is the true parameter.

5.5 Confidence Intervals at the Sample Inputs

We apply the KGP method [73], an extension of SPS. We will create a modified algorithm in order to construct guaranteed confidence intervals for f_* at the first n_0 data points. The variable n_0 is a function of n and it must fulfil the following criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} n_0 &\leq n \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n_0 &= \infty \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n_0/n &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{5.5}$$

Remark 5.5.1 *The “optimal” choice of n_0 leading to small intervals is an open question, in practice $n_0 = \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{n})$ often works well.*

Kernel Gradient Perturbation (KGP) builds confidence regions for *ideal* representations. A representation $f \in \mathcal{H}$ is called ideal w.r.t. $\{x_k\}_{k=1}^{n_0}$, if it has the property that $f(x_k) = f_*(x_k)$, for all $k \in [n_0]$.

Remark 5.5.2 *KGP regions are only guaranteed at the observed inputs. KGP cannot provide confidence bands directly.*

Let us consider the following problem, for a given $\lambda \geq 0$:

$$\text{minimize } (y - K_1\theta)^\top(y - K_1\theta) + \lambda\theta^\top K_2\theta,$$

where $K_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_0}$ is the Gram matrix K having the last $n - n_0$ columns removed, and $K_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0 \times n_0}$ is obtained from K_1 by removing its last $n - n_0$ rows. This can be reformulated as a *least squares* problem, $\|v - \Phi\theta\|^2$, by using

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 \\ \sqrt{\lambda} K_2^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad v = \begin{bmatrix} y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $K_2^{\frac{1}{2}}$ denotes the principal, non-negative square root of K_2 , which exists as K_2 is positive semi-definite.

We search for $\tilde{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0}$ *ideal vector*, such that for every $k \in [n_0]$, we have $(K_1\tilde{\theta})(k) = f_*(x_k)$. We can apply the outer approximation approach of SPS to the reformulated problem to build a guaranteed confidence ellipsoid for ideal vector $\tilde{\theta}$. Note that only the first n_0 residuals should be perturbed, when SPS is applied, as we can only reconstruct the first n_0 noise variables [74].

Eventhough the original confidence region construction assumed symmetric noises, as it mainly applied SPS, this assumption can be relaxed. It is in fact enough if we assume A3 and the stochastic guarantees of KGP methods remain valid [73].

Symmetric noises are special cases of A3. Other examples are, e.g., if the noises are *exchangeable*, the group of *permutation* matrices satisfy this property. As A1 guarantees exchangeability, the symmetricity assumption is not needed anymore for the permutation variant. For SPS, the permutation variant was originally proposed in [75].

The construction of SPS then can be recasted with any matrix group that guarantees distributional invariance. For the group of permutations, the construction of ellipsoidal outer approximation remains the same, only matrix Q_i and vector ψ_i changes to

$$Q_i \doteq \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top P_i \Phi, \quad \text{and} \quad \psi_i \doteq \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top P_i y,$$

where P_i is a random (uniform) permutation matrix.

As in the case of sign-changes, if we apply random permutations when we construct a confidence ellipsoid for the ideal vector $\tilde{\theta}$, we should only perturb the indices of the first n_0 residuals, as we can only reconstruct the first n_0 noise terms.

Therefore, we should use matrices

$$G_i = \begin{bmatrix} P_i & 0 \\ 0 & I_{n-d} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $P_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0 \times n_0}$ is a random permutation matrix, and $I_{n-d} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-n_0) \times (n-n_0)}$ is the

identity matrix.

Next, let us define $\varphi_k \doteq (k(x_1, x_k), \dots, k(x_n, x_k))^T$. We know that $f_*(x_k) = \varphi_k^T \tilde{\theta}$, for $k \in [n_0]$, where $\tilde{\theta}$ is the (unknown) parameter vector of the ideal representation. It holds true that for any (rational) probability $\beta \in (0, 1)$ we can construct a confidence ellipsoid, $\tilde{\Theta}_\beta$, such that it contains $\tilde{\theta}$ with probability at least $1 - \beta$. Then, we can construct (probabilistic) upper and lower bounds of $f_*(x_k)$ by maximizing and minimizing $\varphi_k^T \theta$, for $\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_\beta$. Let us introduce

$$\nu_k \doteq \min_{\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_\beta} \varphi_k^T \theta \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_k \doteq \max_{\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_\beta} \varphi_k^T \theta,$$

for all $k \in [n_0]$, which (convex) problems have analytical solutions, as we have shown in Lemma 5.4.1. Then, the intervals $[\nu_k, \mu_k]$, for $k \in [n_0]$, are simultaneous confidence intervals for the first n_0 functions values, $f_*(x_k)$, for $k \in [n_0]$. That is

$$\mathbb{P}(\forall k \in [n_0] : f_*(x_k) \in [\nu_k, \mu_k]) \geq 1 - \beta. \quad (5.6)$$

5.6 Experiments

The proposed algorithm was also implemented. The Paley-Wiener RKHS was used with parameter $\eta = 30$. The “true” data-generating function was constructed as follows: first, 20 random input points $\{\bar{x}_k\}_{k=1}^{20}$ were generated, with uniform distribution on $[0, 1]$. Then $f_*(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{20} w_k k(x, \bar{x}_k)$ was created, where each w_k had uniform distribution on $[-1, 1]$. The function was normalized, in case its maximum value exceeded 1.

We have generated $n = 200$ noisy observations from f_* . The measurement noise had Gamma distribution with parameters shape $k = 0.5$ and scale $\theta = 0.5$. Eventhough this distribution is not symmetric, its expected value is 0 and it satisfies A3. We compared our results on different significance levels. Figure 5.1 shows that the confidence intervals provide informative bounds for the selected data points.

Figure 5.1: Confidence intervals at some chosen sample (observed) inputs.

5.7 Overview of the Construction

In this section, we briefly overview the main steps of our general nonparametric construction of the confidence bands at a given x_0 query input point.

- (i) First, we build a guaranteed *simultaneous confidence set* for some of true (noise-free) outputs of the target function at the *observed* inputs. Namely, we construct a set $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_0}$ that stochastically guarantees to contain $f_*(x_k)$, for $k \in [n_0]$, where $n_0 \leq n$ is user-chosen (as the data is i.i.d; it is w.l.o.g. that we use the first n_0). This is a nontrivial task, nonetheless it is “easier” than constructing a confidence band for the *whole* function. For this step, e.g., we can build on the results of [73].
- (ii) Using the confidence set $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_0}$ for the true values of f_* at some *observed* inputs, constructed in step (i), we calculate a high probability *upper bound*, τ , for the kernel *norm* (square) of the true function (recall that this norm is a smoothness measure of the target function).
- (iii) Then, for each *input query* point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, we can construct a *confidence interval* for $f_*(x_0)$ as follows. We keep a candidate value z_0 in the confidence region *if and only if* there is a $z = (z_1, \dots, z_{n_0})^\top \in \Theta$, such that the *minimum norm interpolation*

Table 5.1: Summary of the cases and their theoretical guarantees

Input distribution	Output measurements	Type I error	Type II error
		Coverage of the bands	Consistency of the bands
known	noise-free	non-asymptotic	strong, uniform
known	noisy	non-asymptotic	strong, uniform
unknown	noise-free	asymptotic	strong, uniform
unknown	noisy	asymptotic	strong, uniform

of the dataset $\{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0} \cup \{(x_0, z_0)\}$ has a norm (square) less than or equal to τ (i.e., our upper bound for $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$).

In order to make this approach practical, apart from the method in (i), we need a way to guarantee an upper bound for the norm (square) of the true function. Additionally, we also need to give an efficient method to compute the endpoints of the confidence intervals for any query input $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

We will investigate four variants of the approach depending on whether the distribution of the inputs is known and whether the output measurements are noisy. The four cases with their theoretical guarantees are summarized by Table 5.1.

Remark 5.7.1 *Step (i) is superfluous in those cases, when there are no measurement noises, that is if $\varepsilon_k = 0$ for $k \in [n]$, since then we can directly work with $\Theta = \{f_*(x_k)\}$.*

Chapter 6

Nonparametric Confidence Bands: Known Input Distribution

We present our core results in two main chapters: here, we will assume, that the distribution function behind the inputs is a priori known. First, we solve the task for the case when the outputs are observed “perfectly”, then we generalize the result to include observation noise terms. We aim to provide a guaranteed upper bound for the (kernel) norm of the regression function, then we construct a method for the confidence bands. Finally, strong uniform consistency is proven in both cases.

6.1 Noise-free Outputs

First, we start with a simplified problem. In this case, we assume that we perfectly observe the regression function at random inputs (no measurement noises); furthermore, we also assume that we have a priori knowledge of the input density, h_* .

In this noise-free setup, we can recall the Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem, according to which a band-limited function can be perfectly reconstructed from the (equidistant) samples, assuming that the sampling rate exceeds twice the maximum frequency.

However, if we just have few random observations, we may still would like to have at least a region estimate.

To estimate $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$, we can apply *importance sampling* [76]. By the *strong law of large numbers* (SLLN), if $\{x_k\}$ are i.i.d. random variables with probability density h_* , then

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{h_*(x_1)} \right] = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f_*^2(t)}{h_*(t)} h_*(t) dt = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_*^2(t) dt = \|f_*\|_2^2 = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2. \quad (6.1)$$

Based on this idea, we can construct an (guaranteed) upper bound for the norm (square) of the regression function.

Lemma 6.1.1 *Assume A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of input density h_* , and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. Then, for any user-chosen risk probability $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

with the following choice of the upper bound κ :

$$\kappa \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{y_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n}}.$$

Proof Let us introduce the notation

$$R \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{y_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)}.$$

We have $\mathbb{E}[R] = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$. Then, from Hoeffding's inequality,

$$\mathbb{P}(R - \mathbb{E}[R] \leq -t) \leq \exp(-2nt^2/\rho^2).$$

By using the complement rule, we obtain

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathbb{E}[R] < R + t) \geq 1 - \exp(-2nt^2/\rho^2).$$

We would like to choose a threshold $t > 0$ such that

$$1 - \alpha \leq \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{E}[R] < R + t).$$

The above inequality is satisfied, if we choose t as

$$1 - \alpha \leq 1 - \exp(-2nt^2/\rho^2) \implies \exp(-2nt^2/\rho^2) \leq \alpha.$$

By taking the natural logarithm on each side:

$$-2nt^2/\rho^2 \leq \ln(\alpha) \implies t^2 \geq \frac{\ln(\alpha)\rho^2}{-2n} \implies t \geq \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n}}.$$

By choosing $t^* \doteq \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n}} = \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n}}$, we get that

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \geq R + t^*) \leq \alpha,$$

which completes the proof. □

Next, we will provide the method for constructing a confidence interval for any given input query point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$. If $x_0 = x_k$ for any $k \in [n]$, the confidence interval for x_0 will be $I_1(x_0) = I_2(x_0) = y_k$. Else, we follow the next steps:

- (i) The Gram matrix is extended with x_0 , namely, for $i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n$,

$$K_0(i + 1, j + 1) \doteq k(x_i, x_j).$$

Figure 6.1: Construction of the confidence interval for a query input.

- (ii) We compute the highest and the lowest y_0 values which can be interpolated with a function from \mathcal{H} having at most norm square κ .
- (iii) This leads to the following *two* optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min / \max \quad y_0 \\ & \text{subject to} \quad (y_0, y^T) K_0^{-1} (y_0, y^T)^T \leq \kappa \end{aligned} \tag{6.2}$$

where “min / max” means that we have to solve the problem as a minimization and also as a maximization (separately).

- (iv) The optimal values, denoted by y_{\min} and y_{\max} , respectively, determine the *endpoints* of the confidence interval for $f_*(x_0)$, that is $I_1(x_0) \doteq y_{\min}$ and $I_2(x_0) \doteq y_{\max}$. If there is no solution, we return $I(x_0) = \emptyset$. The problems in (6.2) are convex, moreover, we will show that their solutions can be calculated analytically.

Figure 6.1 shows the core idea of the algorithm. For the query x_0 input point, the minimum and the maximum y_0 value, which satisfies (6.2) specifies the endpoints of the constructed confidence interval.

Remark 6.1.1 *Since the output query point y_0 is arbitrary, by using the results of Theorem 3.8.1, we can compute the minimum norm needed to interpolate the original dataset extended by (x_0, y_0) for any candidate y_0 . Building on these results, by having a bound κ*

on the norm square of f_* , in step (ii), we can compute the highest and lowest y_0 values which can be interpolated with a function from \mathcal{H} having at most norm square κ .

Note that the only decision variable of these problems is y_0 , everything else is constant (including the input x_0 , which is also given). Let us partition the inverse Gramian, K_0^{-1} .

$$\begin{bmatrix} c & b^\top \\ b & A \end{bmatrix} \doteq K_0^{-1},$$

where $c \in \mathbb{R}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$; after which

$$(y_0, y^\top) K_0^{-1} (y_0, y^\top)^\top = c y_0^2 + 2 b^\top y y_0 + y^\top A y.$$

Then, introducing $a_0 \doteq c$, $b_0 \doteq 2b^\top y$ and $c_0 = y^\top A y - \kappa$, the two optimization problems (6.2) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \min / \max \quad & y_0 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & a_0 y_0^2 + b_0 y_0 + c_0 \leq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{6.3}$$

in which a_0 , b_0 and c_0 are constants (w.r.t. the optimization).

Since these are (convex) quadratic programming problems (with linear objectives), their optimal solutions must be on the boundary of the constraint. We will prove this with the technique of Lagrange multipliers.

First, we introduce a (real) slack variable s by which the inequality constraint from (6.3) can be transformed into an equality one:

$$a_0 y_0^2 + b_0 y_0 + c_0 + s^2 = 0.$$

Here, we only study the maximization problem, a straightforward modification applies to the minimization case. The Lagrangian of the maximization variant of the problem is

$$L(y_0, s, \lambda) = y_0 - \lambda(a_0 y_0^2 + b_0 y_0 + c_0 + s^2),$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ is a Lagrange multiplier. It is well-known that the necessary conditions for the optimality of $\bar{y}_0, \bar{s}, \bar{\lambda}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} L(\bar{y}_0, \bar{s}, \bar{\lambda}) &= 1 - 2\bar{\lambda} a_0 \bar{y}_0 - \bar{\lambda} b_0 = 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial s} L(\bar{y}_0, \bar{s}, \bar{\lambda}) &= -2\bar{\lambda} \bar{s} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} L(\bar{y}_0, \bar{s}, \bar{\lambda}) &= -a_0 \bar{y}_0^2 - b_0 \bar{y}_0 - c_0 - \bar{s}^2 = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{6.4}$$

The second formula of (6.4) tells us that $\bar{\lambda} \cdot \bar{s} = 0$, hence either $\bar{s} = 0$ or $\bar{\lambda} = 0$. Suppose, that $\bar{\lambda} = 0$. If this holds, the first condition yields $1 - 2 \cdot 0 \cdot a_0 \bar{y}_0 - 0 \cdot b_0 = 0$, which is

a contradiction. This means that $\bar{\lambda} \neq 0$, thus $\bar{s} = 0$ must hold and so the constraint of (6.3) must be satisfied with equality.

We can conclude our results with the following theorem.

Theorem 6.1.2 *Assume A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. For any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ risk probability and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the confidence band guarantees*

$$\nu(\mathcal{I}_n) \geq 1 - \alpha.$$

Proof According to Lemma 6.1.1, the following inequality holds:

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa) \geq 1 - \alpha.$$

If $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa$, then for all $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, for which $x_0 \neq x_k$ for $k \in [n]$, the value $f_*(x_0)$ is in the confidence band, since the function f_* interpolates the sample extended with $(x_0, f_*(x_0))$, and since $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa$, the minimum norm interpolant of this extended sample inherits this norm bound. \square

Observation 6.1.1 *Theorem 6.1.2 provides a finite sample guarantee.*

Next, we will prove that the construction not only guarantees the inclusion of the regression function with a chosen probability, but that the resulting confidence bands are strongly uniformly consistent.

First, we will show that the norm estimation provided by Lemma 6.1.1 is ‘‘consistent’’ in the sense that it converges to the original norm as we obtain more data. Let us denote the original norm of the regression function with $\kappa_* \doteq \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Lemma 6.1.3 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$, the norm estimation obtained by the formula*

$$\kappa_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{y_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n}}.$$

is consistent in the sense that

$$\kappa_n \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \kappa_*$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof We can divide κ_n into the sum of two different parts:

$$\kappa_{n,1} \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{y_k^2}{h_*(x_k)}, \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_{n,2} \doteq \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n}}.$$

It can be clearly seen that $\kappa_{n,2} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. By the strong law of large numbers, it holds true that $\kappa_{n,1} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \kappa_*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, which completes our proof. \square

Recall, that for the dataset $\mathcal{Z}_n \doteq \{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$, where the inputs $\{x_k\}$ are distinct (which almost surely happens under the assumption of A1), the element from \mathcal{H} , which interpolates every y_k output and the matching x_k input has the minimum norm,

$$\hat{f}_n \doteq \arg \min \{ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} : f \in \mathcal{H} \ \& \ \forall k \in [n] : f(x_k) = y_k \},$$

and it takes on the following form for all possible inputs $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$:

$$\hat{f}_n(x) \doteq \sum_{k=1}^n \hat{\alpha}_k k(x, x_k),$$

where the weights are $\hat{\alpha} = K^{-1}y$ with $y \doteq (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T$ and $\hat{\alpha} \doteq (\hat{\alpha}_1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_n)$. Next, we will introduce the following notion: if the function f *interpolates* the data set \mathcal{Z}_n , then we denote it by $f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n$. That is, $f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \iff \forall k \in [n] : f(x_k) = y_k$.

Observation 6.1.2 *Since for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\forall f \in \mathcal{H} : f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \implies \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$, we also have $\|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$, as we obviously have that $f_* \cong \mathcal{Z}_n$.*

By construction, our (abstract) confidence regions in the RKHS are defined as

$$\mathcal{C}_n \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} \mid f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \ \& \ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_n \}. \quad (6.5)$$

Note that if we construct the confidence bands separately for each input, we get

$$\bar{\mathcal{C}}_n \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} \mid \forall x \in \mathbb{R}^d : I_1(x) \leq f(x) \leq I_2(x) \}, \quad (6.6)$$

where the interval endpoints defined according to (6.2), that is

$$I_1(x) = \min_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} f(x), \quad \text{and} \quad I_2(x) = \max_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} f(x), \quad (6.7)$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. From this, we immediately have that $\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq \bar{\mathcal{C}}_n$. Moreover:

Theorem 6.1.4 *Let \mathcal{H} be any RKHS of $\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ functions with a bounded kernel k . Let $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$ be a confidence region sequence in \mathcal{H} , such that with probability one, we have*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} \|f - f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}} = 0.$$

Let $\{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_n\}$ be a confidence band sequence defined by (6.6) and (6.7). Then, we have (a.s.)

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |I_1(x) - f_*(x)| = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |I_2(x) - f_*(x)| = 0.$$

Proof Let us denote the bound on the kernel by B , that is

$$B \doteq \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} k(x, x) < \infty.$$

We can recall that for any $f \in \mathcal{H}$ and any $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the reproducing property and the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality imply

$$|f(x)| = |\langle f, k(\cdot, x) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}| \leq \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} \|k(\cdot, x)\|_{\mathcal{H}} = \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} \sqrt{k(x, x)}.$$

Hence, in our case, using the bound on the kernel

$$\|f\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |f(x)| \leq \sqrt{B} \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}.$$

Then, with probability one we have, as $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\sup_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} \|f - f_*\|_{\infty} \leq \sqrt{B} \sup_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} \|f - f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, for each $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, using the construction of $I_1(x)$ and $I_2(x)$,

$$|I_1(x) - f_*(x)| = \left| \min_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} f(x) - f_*(x) \right| \leq \sup_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} |f(x) - f_*(x)|,$$

and similarly for $I_2(x)$. Taking “sup” over all $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ yields

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |I_1(x) - f_*(x)| \leq \sup_{f \in \mathcal{C}_n} \|f - f_*\|_{\infty} \rightarrow 0,$$

with probability one, and similarly for $I_2(x)$. This completes the proof. \square

Therefore, from the strong uniform consistency of our abstract confidence regions, that is $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$, defined by (6.5), the strong uniform consistency of the pointwise built confidence bands, $\{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n\}$, defined by (6.6) and (6.7), follows. Henceforth, we will focus on $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$.

Since we typically have $\mathbb{P}(f_* \in \mathcal{C}_n) < 1$, for our theoretical analysis of strong consistency we need to extend \mathcal{C}_n to guarantee the inclusion of the regression function, f_* . We achieve this by changing the norm term to $\tilde{\kappa}_n \doteq \max\{\kappa_*, \kappa_n\}$. Then, let

$$\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \ \& \ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\kappa}_n\}.$$

Observation 6.1.3 *The functions f_* and \hat{f}_n are both elements of $\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$ and $\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$.*

This observation follows from the fact that f_* is the original data-generating function, hence $f_*(x_k) = y_k$ holds for each $k \in [n]$, and $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \kappa^*$. The function \hat{f}_n also interpolates \mathcal{Z}_n by definition and $\|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa^*$. Also, since $\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, we have $\|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|f'\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$, for all $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$, by Observation 6.1.2. Since $\kappa_n \leq \tilde{\kappa}_n$, we have $\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$.

Let $\mathcal{H}_n \doteq \text{span}\{k(\cdot, x_i) : i \in [n]\}$.

Observation 6.1.4 *\mathcal{H}_n is a closed subspace of \mathcal{H} , since it is finite dimensional.*

From the Hilbert projection theorem [77], for any $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$, it follows that

$$f' = f'_{\parallel} + f'_{\perp},$$

where $f'_{\parallel} \in \mathcal{H}_n$ and $f'_{\perp} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{\perp}$; moreover, this decomposition is unique.

Lemma 6.1.5 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ holds for $k \in [n]$, for every $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$, it holds true that $f'_{\parallel} = \hat{f}_n$.*

Proof First, we prove that $\forall i \in [n] : f'(x_i) = f'_{\parallel}(x_i)$. By using the reproducing property,

$$\begin{aligned} f'(x_i) &= \langle f', k(\cdot, x_i) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \langle f'_{\parallel} + f'_{\perp}, k(\cdot, x_i) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \underbrace{\langle f'_{\parallel}, k(\cdot, x_i) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}}_{f'_{\parallel}(x_i)} + \underbrace{\langle f'_{\perp}, k(\cdot, x_i) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}}_0 \\ &= f'_{\parallel}(x_i), \end{aligned}$$

where $\langle f'_{\perp}, k(\cdot, x_i) \rangle = 0$, since $k(\cdot, x_i) \in \mathcal{H}_n$. Therefore, for all $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$, we have $f'_{\parallel}(x_i) = f_*(x_i)$, for $i \in [n]$. In other words, since $f'_{\parallel} \in \mathcal{H}_n$, we have

$$f_*(x_i) = f'_{\parallel}(x_i) = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k k(x_i, x_k),$$

for $i \in [n]$. However, there is only one function in \mathcal{H}_n which can guarantee this property, namely \hat{f}_n . To see this, notice that the coefficients must satisfy equation $K\alpha = y$, where $y^T = [y_1, \dots, y_n]$ and K is the Gram matrix. Therefore, the solution is $\alpha = K^{-1}y$, since K is (a.s.) invertible. This function, by definition, is the interpolant \hat{f}_n . \square

By introducing $\hat{\kappa}_n \doteq \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$, from Lemma 6.1.5, we obtain the following: for any $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\kappa}_n &= \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|f'\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \|f'_{\parallel} + f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \\ &= \|f'_{\parallel}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\kappa}_n. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have

$$\|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\kappa}_n - \hat{\kappa}_n.$$

Lemma 6.1.6 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ holds for $k \in [n]$, we have*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n \subseteq \mathcal{B}(f_*, 2\sqrt{(\tilde{\kappa}_n - \hat{\kappa}_n)}),$$

where $\tilde{\kappa}_n \doteq \max\{\kappa_*, \kappa_n\}$ and $\hat{\kappa}_n \doteq \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Proof For an arbitrary $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$, using Lemma 6.1.5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|f^* - f'\|_{\mathcal{H}} &= \|f_{\parallel}^* + f_{\perp}^* - f'_{\parallel} - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \|\hat{f}_n + f_{\perp}^* - \hat{f}_n - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \|f_{\perp}^* - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &\leq \|f_{\perp}^*\|_{\mathcal{H}} + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &\leq 2\sqrt{(\tilde{\kappa}_n - \hat{\kappa}_n)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

We conclude the result in the following theorem.

Theorem 6.1.7 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ holds for $k \in [n]$, the constructed confidence bands, $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$, are strongly uniformly consistent, that is*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{n=k}^{\infty} \{\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq B(f_*, \varepsilon)\}\right) = 1.$$

Proof It holds true that $\mathcal{C}_n \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n \subseteq \mathcal{B}(f_*, 2\sqrt{\tilde{\kappa}_n - \hat{\kappa}_n})$ and $2\sqrt{(\tilde{\kappa}_n - \hat{\kappa}_n)} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. The last claim follows from Lemma 6.1.3 and the fact that $\hat{\kappa}_n \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \kappa_*$ [27]. □

6.2 Noisy Outputs

Next, we aim to generalize the previous result for the case of outputs with measurement noise, satisfying A3. Recall, that by using the algorithm from Section 5.5, we can construct guaranteed confidence intervals for the first n_0 inputs, where n_0 satisfies (5.5). From (5.6), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n_0} f_*^2(x_k) \leq \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \max\{\nu_k^2, \mu_k^2\}, \quad (6.8)$$

with probability at least $1 - \beta$. We introduce the notation $M_{n,k}^2 \doteq \max\{\nu_k^2, \mu_k^2\}$. We aim to use this term to provide a stochastically guaranteed upper bound for $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Lemma 6.2.1 *By assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, the a priori knowledge of h_* , and that the confidence intervals $[\nu_k, \mu_k]$, for $k \in [n_0]$ satisfy (5.6). Then, for any user-chosen risk probabilities $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$, we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau) \geq 1 - \alpha - \beta,$$

with the following choice of the upper bound τ :

$$\tau \doteq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{M_{n,k}^2}{h_*(x_k)} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n_0}}.$$

The proof follows from (6.8), Lemma 6.1.1 and Boole's inequality (the union bound).

Next, we will construct a confidence interval for any given input query point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, for which $x_0 \neq x_k$ for $k \in [n_0]$.

- (i) The Gram matrix of the first n_0 inputs is extended with x_0 , namely

$$\tilde{K}_0(i+1, j+1) \doteq k(x_i, x_j),$$

for $i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n_0$.

- (ii) We solve the two following (convex) optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} \min / \max \quad & z_0 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0}) \tilde{K}_0^{-1}(z_0, \dots, z_{n_0})^T \leq \tau \\ & \nu_1 \leq z_1 \leq \mu_1, \dots, \nu_{n_0} \leq z_{n_0} \leq \mu_{n_0} \end{aligned} \quad (6.9)$$

where “min / max” again means that the problem have to be solved as a minimization and as a maximization (separately).

- (iii) The optimal values, denoted by z_{\min} and z_{\max} , are the *endpoints* of the confidence interval: $I_1(x_0) \doteq z_{\min}$, and $I_2(x_0) \doteq z_{\max}$. If (6.9) is infeasible, e.g., we get an empty KGP ellipsoid, we set $I(x_0) = \emptyset$.

Even though the solutions of (6.9) provide suitable confidence bands for the regression function, these results can be refined. The refinements come in two parts: first, we present a more efficient way to provide a stochastic upper bound for the norm of the regression function. Next, we will refine the confidence interval constructions in (6.9).

The main idea behind the construction is the following: the original method could lead to conservative results, due to the fact that the intervals $[\nu_k, \mu_k]$, for $k \in [n_0]$, are constructed independently, as if choosing a function value at an input could not influence the choice of function values at other inputs.

Assume for simplicity that $\lambda = 0$ in (3.6). Then $\Phi = K_1$ and the ellipsoidal outer approximation takes the following form:

$$\hat{\Theta}_\beta \doteq \{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^n : (\theta - \hat{\theta})^T (1/n) K_1^T K_1 (\theta - \hat{\theta}) \leq \gamma^* \}, \quad (6.10)$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ is the LS estimate, $K_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_0}$ is the Gram matrix K having the last $n - n_0$ columns removed, and β is a risk probability.

After dividing both sides of (6.10) by γ^* , and by introducing $H \doteq \frac{1}{n\gamma^*} K_1^T K_1$, the confidence ellipsoid becomes

$$\hat{\Theta}_\beta \doteq \{ \theta \in \mathbb{R}^n : (\theta - \hat{\theta})^T H (\theta - \hat{\theta}) \leq 1 \}, \quad (6.11)$$

This ellipsoid contains (with high probability) the *coefficients* of the ideal representation. The function values of the ideal representation can be calculated using the matrix K_2 , where $K_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0 \times n_0}$ is K_1 having the last $n - n_0$ rows removed. Hence, in order to get a confidence ellipsoid for the *function values* at the first n_0 inputs, we need to transform ellipsoid (6.11) by K_2 . By multiplying both sides of (6.11) by K_2 , the Hessian of the ellipsoid becomes $K_2^{-1}HK_2^{-1}$, and the center will be $K_2\hat{\theta}$. Finally, we arrived at

$$\mathcal{Z} \doteq \{ z \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0} : (z - K_2\hat{\theta})^T K_2^{-1}HK_2^{-1}(z - K_2\hat{\theta}) \leq 1 \},$$

which, by construction, has the property that

$$\mathbb{P}((f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^T \in \mathcal{Z}) \geq 1 - \beta. \quad (6.12)$$

With this construction, we can provide an improved upper bound for the kernel norm of the regression function. Let us introduce the notation $z \doteq (z_1, \dots, z_d)$. Instead of using the absolute maximum of every single n_0 data points, we can solve an optimization problem with respect to \mathcal{Z} as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && -\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{z_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} \\ & \text{subject to} && z \in \mathcal{Z} \end{aligned} \quad (6.13)$$

This problem is not convex, but thanks to strong duality, we can solve the dual problem instead [78]. Let us study the constraint of (6.13), namely $z \in \mathcal{Z}$: This term can also be written as follows:

$$(z - K_2\hat{\theta})^T K_2^{-1}HK_2^{-1}(z - K_2\hat{\theta}) \leq 1.$$

By introducing the notion $V \doteq K_2^{-1}PK_2^{-1}$, and subtracting 1 from each side, the inequality becomes

$$(z - K_2\hat{\theta})^T V(z - K_2\hat{\theta}) - 1 \leq 0,$$

since K_2 is symmetric. After expanding the expression above, we obtain

$$z^T Vz - z^T VK_2\hat{\theta} - (K_2\hat{\theta})^T Vz + (K_2\hat{\theta})^T VK_2\hat{\theta} - 1 \leq 0.$$

Since we know that K_2 is a symmetric matrix, we have

$$z^T Vz - 2\hat{\theta}^T K_2 Vz + \hat{\theta}^T K_2^T VK_2\hat{\theta} - 1 \leq 0.$$

By substituting back $V = K_2^{-1}HK_2^{-1}$, we get

$$z^T K_2^{-1} H K_2^{-1} z - 2 \widehat{\theta}^T H K_2^{-1} z + \widehat{\theta}^T H \widehat{\theta} - 1 \leq 0.$$

By introducing $A_1 \doteq K_2^{-1} H K_2^{-1}$, $b_1^T \doteq -\widehat{\theta}^T H K_2^{-1}$, and $c_1 \doteq \widehat{\theta}^T H \widehat{\theta} - 1$, the constraint of (6.13) can be written as

$$z^T A_1 z + 2 b_1^T z + c_1 \leq 0.$$

With this notation, we can apply a result from [78] about the dual of (even nonconvex) quadratic problems that have only one quadratic constraint to get

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && \xi \\ & \text{subject to} && \rho \geq 0 \\ & && \begin{bmatrix} A_0 + \rho A_1 & \rho b_1 \\ \rho b_1^T & \rho c_1 - \xi \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \end{aligned} \tag{6.14}$$

where $A_0 \doteq -\frac{1}{n_0} I$ comes from the optimization objective.

Problem (6.14) is always convex and can be computed efficiently. If we denote the optimal solution by ξ^* , then the upper bound for the norm square of f_* is the following:

$$\tau_0 \doteq \xi^* + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n_0}}. \tag{6.15}$$

We conclude this result in the following lemma.

Lemma 6.2.2 *Assume A1, A2, A3, A4 and the a priori knowledge of h_* . Then, for any $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$ risk probabilities,*

$$\mathbb{P}((f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^T \in \mathcal{Z} \wedge \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau_0) \geq 1 - \alpha - \beta.$$

We have constructed ellipsoid \mathcal{Z} to satisfy property (6.12). Using this, we can also refine the confidence interval construction problem(s) presented by (6.9): the box constraints given by the confidence intervals should be replaced by an ellipsoidal constraint:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min / \max && z_0 \\ & \text{subject to} && (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0}) K_0^{-1} (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0})^T \leq \tau_0 \\ & && (z_1, \dots, z_{n_0}) \in \mathcal{Z}, \end{aligned} \tag{6.16}$$

where we also used the improved norm bound τ_0 . These problems are also convex. The following theorem summarizes the guarantee of this construction.

Theorem 6.2.3 *Assume that A1, A2, A3, A4 are satisfied and the a priori knowledge of h_* . Let $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$ be given risk probabilities. Then, for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the confidence*

band described above guarantees

$$\nu(\mathcal{I}_n) \geq 1 - \alpha - \beta.$$

Proof Let us introduce the following event:

$$A \doteq \{(f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^\top \in \mathcal{Z} \wedge \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau\}.$$

According to Lemma 6.2.2, the event A has probability at least $1 - \alpha - \beta$.

Conditioning on event A , for all query input point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$ such that K_0 is invertible, which holds a.e., we can guarantee that there is a $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, namely $z = (f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^\top$, and z_0 , name $z_0 = f_*(x_0)$, such that the *minimum norm* interpolant of $\{(x_0, z_0)\} \cup \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0}$ has a norm square less or equal than τ , since f_* itself is an interpolant of this dataset. Thus, we have that $z_{\min} \leq z_0 \leq z_{\max}$, for $z_0 = f_*(x_0)$. This property is always guaranteed, hence, we *simultaneously* have for \mathbb{P}_X -a.e. $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$ that $z_{\min}(x_0) \leq f_*(x_0) \leq z_{\max}(x_0)$, under A . \square

Next, we prove that the refined confidence bands provided by (6.16) are less conservative than the confidence sets given by (6.9) in the following sense:

Lemma 6.2.4 *Assuming A1, A2, A3 and A4, the following statements hold true:*

$$\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \times_{i=1}^{n_0} [\nu_i, \mu_i], \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_0 \leq \tau.$$

Proof The original SPS method provides a n_0 -dimensional ellipsoid $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_0}$ with the following statistical guarantee:

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in E) \geq 1 - \beta,$$

where θ^* is the true parameter and $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is an user-chosen risk parameter. Since \mathcal{H} is an RKHS and k is strictly positive definite, it holds that

$$\exists \theta^* : K_2 \theta^* = [f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0})]^\top,$$

where $K_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_0 \times n_0}$ is K_1 having the last $n - n_0$ rows and columns removed. If we only wanted to obtain the value of a certain $f_*(x_i)$ for a given $i \in [n_0]$, we can write

$$e_i^\top K_2 \theta^* = f_*(x_i),$$

where $e_i \doteq [0, 0, \dots, 1, 0, 0, \dots, 0]^\top$ is the i th canonical basis vector.

The pair ν_i, μ_i for $i \in [n_0]$ is defined by the following (convex) optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_i &\doteq \min \{ e_i^\top K_2 : \theta \in E \}, \\ \mu_i &\doteq \max \{ e_i^\top K_2 : \theta \in E \}. \end{aligned}$$

First, suppose that $\underline{z} \in \mathcal{Z}$ is fixed (i.e., constant). By definition, it follows that there exists a corresponding $\underline{\theta} \in E$, such that $\underline{z} = K_2 \underline{\theta}$. Now, let us fix an index $\underline{i} \in [n_0]$, and then let us introduce the following notation: $\underline{z}_{\underline{i}} \doteq e_{\underline{i}}^T \underline{z} = e_{\underline{i}}^T K_2 \underline{\theta}$.

We need to show, that for the fixed $\underline{i} \in [n_0]$, it holds that $\underline{z}_{\underline{i}} \in [\nu_{\underline{i}}, \mu_{\underline{i}}]$. This holds by definition, since we have

$$\nu_{\underline{i}} = \min_{\theta \in E} e_{\underline{i}}^T K_2 \theta \leq e_{\underline{i}}^T K_2 \underline{\theta} = \underline{z}_{\underline{i}} = e_{\underline{i}}^T K_2 \underline{\theta} \leq \max_{\theta \in E} e_{\underline{i}}^T K_2 \theta = \mu_{\underline{i}}.$$

Since, this is true for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ and $i \in [n_0]$, we have that $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \times_{i=1}^{n_0} [\nu_i, \mu_i]$.

For the second part of the lemma, we can write out the definitions of τ and τ_0 :

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{i=1}^{n_0} \frac{z_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} \mid z \in \times_{i=1}^{n_0} [\nu_i, \mu_i] \right\} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n_0}} \\ \tau_0 &= \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{i=1}^{n_0} \frac{z_k^2}{h_*(x_k)} \mid z \in \mathcal{Z} \right\} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n_0}} \end{aligned}$$

By using the first claim, it holds that $\tau_0 \leq \tau$. □

Definition 6.2.1 For a given $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, the α -level confidence set for the sample X

$$\mathbb{P}(f_* \in C_\alpha(X)) \geq 1 - \alpha$$

is smaller than a different C'_α confidence set if

$$\mathbb{P}(f_* \in C'_\alpha(X)) \geq 1 - \alpha$$

holds and $C_\alpha(X) \subseteq C'_\alpha(X)$ almost surely.

Observation 6.2.1 Using Lemma 6.2.4, we conclude that the refined confidence bands constructed by (6.16) are smaller than the confidence bands constructed by (6.9).

Finally, we will prove that uniform strong consistency holds true with an additional technical assumption. Let $V_{n,k}$ denote the proportional error in the confidence intervals for the k -th input from the set $\{x_1, \dots, x_{n_0}\}$, namely:

$$V_{n,k} \doteq \frac{M_{n,k}^2}{f_*^2(x_k)}.$$

Observation 6.2.2 In $V_{n,k}$, the denominator contains the values of $f_*^2(x_k)$. Since f_* is a band-limited function, under A4 it is guaranteed that $f_* \neq 0$, therefore, $\mathbb{P}(f_*(x) \neq 0) = 1$.

We make the following assumption.

A5 If $\tilde{V}_n \doteq \max\{V_{n,1}, \dots, V_{n,n_0}\}$ and $\bar{V}_n \doteq \min\{V_{n,1}, \dots, V_{n,n_0}\}$, then it holds that

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{V}_n = 1\right) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{P}\left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \bar{V}_n = 1\right) = 1.$$

A5 states that the constructed confidence intervals for the n_0 input points are consistent in the sense that both their maximum and minimum proportional error almost surely converges to 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Assuming A5, we obtain:

$$\bar{V}_n \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)} \leq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{M_{n,k}^2}{h_*(x_k)} = \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{f_*^2(x_k) \cdot V_{n,k}}{h_*(x_k)} \leq \tilde{V}_n \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)}. \quad (6.17)$$

Next, we will prove that the norm estimation provided by Lemma 6.2.1 converges to the original norm as we obtain more data.

Lemma 6.2.5 *Assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 and the a priori knowledge of h_* , the norm estimation obtained by the formula*

$$\tau_n \doteq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{M_{n,k}^2}{h_*(x_k)} + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n_0}}$$

is consistent in the sense that, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\tau_n \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \kappa_*.$$

Proof Bound τ_n is the sum of two terms:

$$\tau_{n,1} \doteq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{M_{n,k}^2}{h_*(x_k)}, \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{n,2} \doteq \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n_0}}.$$

We clearly have that $\tau_{n,2} \rightarrow 0$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n_0 = \infty$ from (5.5). Next, we need to prove that $\tau_{n,1} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \kappa_*$. By using A5 and the strong law of large numbers,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \bar{V}_n \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{V}_n \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{h_*(x_k)} = \|f_*\|_2^2 = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

Then, by using (6.17), it follows that $\tau_{n,1} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \kappa_*$ □

Observation 6.2.3 *In the case of noisy outputs, the constructed confidence bands are also constructed separately for each input. By using the result of Theorem 6.1.4, and from the strong uniform consistency of our abstract confidence regions, the strong uniform consistency of the pointwise built confidence bands follows.*

Let us introduce the notations $\mathcal{R}_n = \times_{k=1}^{n_0} [\nu_k, \mu_k]$ and $z_* \doteq [f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0})]^T$. By

using (6.12), we are able to provide a set $\mathcal{Z}_n \subseteq \mathcal{R}_n \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_0}$, which guarantees:

$$\mathbb{P}(z_* \in \mathcal{Z}_n) \geq 1 - \beta.$$

By construction, our confidence bands are defined as

$$\mathcal{D}_n \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : \exists z \in \mathcal{Z}_n : f \cong \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0} \wedge \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau_n\}.$$

Since $\mathbb{P}(f_* \in \mathcal{D}_n) < 1$, we have to extend this set to guarantee the inclusion of f_* . Let $\tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n \doteq \mathcal{Z}_n \cup z_*$, and $\tilde{\tau}_{n_0} \doteq \max\{\tau_{n_0}, \kappa_*\}$; then

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : \exists z \in \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n : f \cong \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0} \wedge \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\tau}_n\},$$

where $k \in [n_0]$ and $z_k \in z$. The main idea behind the set is that we are no longer able to interpolate the “perfectly” observed outputs. Instead, we can only interpolate noisy outputs, however, the constructed confidence intervals guarantee, that the intervals in \mathcal{R}_n are approaching to the noise-free outputs as $n \rightarrow \infty$ thanks to A5.

For a fixed $z \in \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n$, let

$$\hat{f}_{n,z} \doteq \arg \min \{ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} : f \in \mathcal{H} \ \& \ \forall k \in [n_0] : f(x_k) = z_k \},$$

where $z_k \in z$ and $\hat{f}_n \doteq \hat{f}_{n,z_*}$ will denote the minimum norm interpolant for the noise-free outputs. Let $\|\hat{f}_n\| \doteq \hat{\tau}_n$.

Observation 6.2.4 $\|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}} \leq \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}$, hence, f_* and \hat{f}_n are both elements of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$.

This holds true, since both functions interpolate $z_* \in \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n$ by definition and we have $\|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_* = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\tau}_n$.

From the Hilbert projection theorem [77], for any $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$, it follows that

$$f' = f'_{\parallel} + f'_{\perp},$$

where $f'_{\parallel} \in \mathcal{H}_n$ and $f'_{\perp} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{\perp}$; moreover, this decomposition is unique. Recall that $\mathcal{H}_n = \text{span}\{k(\cdot, x_i) : i \in [n]\}$ and it is a closed subspace of \mathcal{H} , since it is finite dimensional.

Lemma 6.2.6 For every $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$, it holds true that $f'_{\parallel} = \hat{f}_{n,z}$, where $z \in \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n$.

The proof is analogous to the proof of Lemma 6.1.5.

From Lemma 6.2.6, we obtain that for any $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$, it holds true that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\hat{f}_{n,z}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 &\leq \|f'\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \|f'_{\parallel} + f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \\ &= \|f'_{\parallel}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \|\hat{f}_{n,z}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\tau}_n. \end{aligned} \tag{6.18}$$

Next, we will introduce the following function:

$$\hat{f}_{n,\nu} \doteq \arg \min \{ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} : f \in \mathcal{H} \ \& \ \forall k \in [n_0] : f(x_k) = \nu_k \}.$$

$\hat{f}_{n,\nu}$ is the minimum norm interpolant from \mathcal{H} , which interpolates the lowest points of the confidence intervals for the first n_0 observations.

Observation 6.2.5 For any $z \in \mathcal{Z}_n$, we have

$$\bar{V}_{*,n}^2 \cdot \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|\bar{V}_n \cdot \hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|\hat{f}_{n,\nu}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \|\hat{f}_{n,z}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

where $\bar{V}_{*,n}$ denotes the minimal element of the set $\{\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2, \dots, \bar{V}_n\}$.

Observation 6.2.6 A5 guarantees that $\bar{V}_{*,n} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 1$ as $n_0 \rightarrow \infty$.

Combining the results of (6.18), Observation 6.2.5 and Observation 6.2.6, we obtain

$$\|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\tau}_n - (\bar{V}_{*,n} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_n,$$

where the \wedge operator chooses the minimum of the two values.

Lemma 6.2.7 Assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 and the a priori knowledge of h_* , we have

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n \subseteq \mathcal{B}\left(f_*, 2\sqrt{\tilde{\tau}_n - (\bar{V}_{*,n} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_n}\right),$$

where $\tilde{\tau}_n \doteq \max\{\kappa_*, \tau_n\}$ and $\hat{\tau}_n \doteq \|\hat{f}_n\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Proof For an arbitrary $f' \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$, using Lemma 6.2.6, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|f^* - f'\|_{\mathcal{H}} &= \|f_{\parallel}^* + f_{\perp}^* - f'_{\parallel} - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \|\hat{f}_n + f_{\perp}^* - \hat{f}_n - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \|f_{\perp}^* - f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &\leq \|f_{\perp}^*\|_{\mathcal{H}} + \|f'_{\perp}\|_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &\leq 2\sqrt{\tilde{\tau}_n - (\bar{V}_{*,n} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_n}. \end{aligned}$$

□

We conclude our results with the following theorem.

Theorem 6.2.8 Assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 and the a priori knowledge of h_* , the constructed confidence bands, $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}$, are strongly uniformly consistent, that is for all $\varepsilon > 0$, we have

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{n=k}^{\infty} \{\mathcal{D}_n \subseteq B(f_*, \varepsilon)\}\right) = 1.$$

Proof The claim of the theorem follows from

$$\mathcal{D}_n \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n \subseteq \mathcal{B}\left(f_*, 2\sqrt{\tilde{\tau}_n - (\bar{V}_{*,n} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_n}\right)$$

and $2\sqrt{\tilde{\tau}_n - (\bar{V}_{*,n} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_n} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. The last claim follows from Lemma 6.2.5, Theorem 6.1.7 and Observation 6.2.6. □

Observation 6.2.7 *We proved strong uniform consistency for the $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}$ confidence bands for the norm estimation term obtained by Lemma 6.2.1. Thanks to Lemma 6.2.4, the proof holds for the refined result as well.*

6.3 Reducing the Computational Complexity

Next, we propose a refined method to improve the computational efficiency of the introduced methods. Even though convex problems are generally efficient to solve, and for the noise-free case, we are also able to obtain analytical solutions, these methods include the computation of K_0^{-1} for every single query input $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, because this matrix depends on x_0 . Computing the inverse for each input could become computationally demanding. Here, we propose an alternative, more efficient solution by using Schur complements. The core idea is that the matrix K_0 is essentially the original K extended by the values induced by x_0 . We argue that we only need to compute K^{-1} once, and then we can use it to compute K_0^{-1} for every query input x_0 .

Observation 6.3.1 *The dimension of K_0 vary depending on whether we work with noise-free or noisy outputs. For the noise-free case, we have $K_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$, and for the noisy case, we have $K_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_0+1) \times (n_0+1)}$, where $n_0 \leq n$. W.l.o.g. we will assume, that we work with the first case.*

Formally, $K_0(x_0)$ can be written as a block matrix,

$$K_0 = \begin{bmatrix} r_0 & k_0 \\ k_0^\top & K \end{bmatrix},$$

where $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $k_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $r_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, with $r_0 = k(x_0, x_0)$ and $k_{0,i} = k(x_0, x_i)$.

By introducing the *Schur complement*

$$g_0 \doteq (K_0/r_0) \doteq r_0 - k_0^\top K^{-1} k_0,$$

we can calculate K_0^{-1} using the following formula [78],

$$K_0^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_0^{-1} & -K^{-1} k_0 g_0^{-1} \\ -g_0^{-1} k_0^\top K^{-1} & K^{-1} + K^{-1} k_0 g_0^{-1} k_0^\top K^{-1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.19)$$

This approach has the advantage that (6.19) can be computed using $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ floating point operations (flops), instead of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ flops, assuming K^{-1} is available. Consequently, we only need to compute the inverse of matrix K once, as an initialization step, and then matrix K^{-1} can be used for each possible query input x_0 to construct the inverse of the corresponding extended kernel matrix K_0 . For a given x_0 , first we need to compute the query point dependent scalar r_0 and vector k_0 , based on which we can calculate the Schur

complement g_0 . Finally, we can apply formula (6.19) to build K_0^{-1} in a computationally efficient way. For example, if $n = 100$, then the speedup of computing the inverse of K_0 , given K^{-1} , could be even $100\times$, depending on the implementation.

Remark 6.3.1 *The convex programs in our algorithms include the inverse of the Gramian matrix that may be numerically unstable for certain kernels, such as the Gaussian kernel. There are various ways to handle this, the simplest is to add a tiny constant times the identity matrix to Gramian before inverting it. Another approach is to use the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) method. Instead of calculating the inverse of the original Gramian matrix, a more stable task is obtained by choosing a threshold parameter, and removing the singular values below that value. Then, we should use pseudo-inverse.*

6.4 Numerical Experiments

The presented algorithms were also tested numerically. For easier demonstration purposes, we investigated the univariate case ($d = 1$) and the Paley-Wiener RKHS. First, the original data-generating function was generated in the following way: 20 random input points $\{\bar{x}_k\}_{k=1}^{20}$ were generated, with uniform distribution on $[-1, 1]$. Then $f_*(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{20} w_k k(x, \bar{x}_k)$ was created, where each w_k followed a Gaussian distribution with mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 1$. The function was normalized, in case its maximum value exceeded 1.

For the case, where the outputs were observed without noise, a sample with $n = 40$ noise-free observations was generated from f_* . The $\{x_k\}$ inputs followed Laplace distribution with location $\mu = 0$ and scale $b = 0.8$. The parameter for the Paley-Wiener RKHS was $\eta = 30$. Figure 6.2 shows that the confidence bands lead to informative and adequate simultaneous confidence bands.

Remark 6.4.1 *If the input query point x_0 equals x_k for any $k \in [n]$, the confidence interval for x_0 is $I_1(x_0) = I_2(x_0) = y_k$. In Figures 6.2 and 7.1, the plotted simultaneous confidence bands are created by fitting a polynomial function to several test points.*

In the case of measurement noises, $n = 300$ observations were used. The $\{x_k\}$ inputs followed Laplace distribution with location $\mu = 0$ and scale $b = 0.5$. The distribution of the $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ noise terms was $\varepsilon \sim \exp(\lambda) - \lambda$ for $\lambda = 0.3$. It is clear that this noise term satisfies A3, since its expected value is 0 and even though it is not symmetric, the method remains feasible. The parameter of the Paley-Wiener RKHS was $\eta = 20$. Figure 6.3 shows that the confidence bands lead to informative and adequate simultaneous confidence bands even with measurement noises affecting the outputs.

Figure 6.2: Simultaneous confidence bands, having coverage probabilities 10 %, 50 % and 90 %, with an a priori known input distribution and noise-free outputs.

Figure 6.3: Simultaneous confidence bands, having coverage probabilities 10 %, 50 % and 90 %, with an a priori known input distribution and noisy outputs (unknown distribution).

Figure 6.4: Comparison with GPR: noise terms with Laplace distribution.

Figure 6.5: Comparison with GPR: noise terms with Gaussian distribution.

We also compared our method with Gaussian process regression. $n = 300$ observations were used from the same $\{x_k\}$ distribution. In the first case, the $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ noise terms followed Laplace distribution location $\mu = 0$ and scale $\sigma = 0.3$. In the second case, the noise terms followed Gaussian distribution mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.3$. The $\{x_k\}$ inputs followed Laplace distribution with location $\mu = 0$ and scale $b = 0.5$. The parameter of the Paley-Wiener RKHS was $\eta = 20$. Figure 6.4 and 6.5 both show that GPR leads to more informative results, however, in the case of noise terms with Laplace distribution, the true regression function was not included in the confidence set.

Chapter 7

Nonparametric Confidence Bands: Unknown Input Distribution

In this chapter, we will focus on building confidence bands for the regression function in the case where there is no (a priori) knowledge of the input distribution. First, we will once again assume, that we perfectly observe the regression function at the inputs, then we generalize the result to the noisy case.

7.1 Noise-free Outputs

Since we no longer assume a priori knowledge of h_* , which is the probability density function of the $\{x_k\}$ inputs, we will have to use an estimation. For solving this task, we are working with two separate datasets: one for providing a guaranteed upper estimation for the kernel norm of the regression function, and one for estimating the unknown density function. This is a case of semi-supervised learning [79, 80]. The prototype sample, which will be denoted by \mathcal{D}'_m , will be used for estimating the density function, while the labeled data set is used for the norm estimation. Obtaining data for the prototype sample is generally an easier task, since we are not required to have input-output pairs. For the density estimation, we are going to use the well-known Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) approach [81, 82]. First, we will define the smoother function.

Definition 7.1.1 (Smoother) *Let k be density function on \mathbb{R}^d (w.r.t. the Lebesgue measure). If $\sup_{u \in \mathbb{R}^d} k(u) < \infty$, then k is called a smoother function.*

These requirements are needed to ensure that the kernel density estimation method will yield a probability density function.

Definition 7.1.2 (Kernel Density Estimation) Let $\mathcal{D}'_m \doteq x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_m$ be an i.i.d. sample drawn from a probability distribution on \mathbb{R}^d with an (unknown) probability density function h_* . The kernel density estimator of this function is the following:

$$\hat{h}_m(x) \doteq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m k_b(x - x_i) = \frac{1}{mb} \sum_{i=1}^m k\left(\frac{x - x_i}{b}\right),$$

where k is the smoother and $b > 0$ is the bandwidth, which is a smoothing parameter.

The bandwidth in this formula is a hyper-parameter and it has a strong effect on the resulting estimation. There are several data-based methods available for choosing this value [83, 84, 85]. If the estimated density is Gaussian, and Gaussian basis functions are used in approximating univariate data, the optimal choice of b has order $n^{-1/5}$ [86].

Next, we are going to introduce two new assumptions.

A6 For the \hat{h}_m kernel density estimation, it holds true that

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |\hat{h}_m(x) - h_*(x)| \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 0 \quad \text{as } m \rightarrow \infty.$$

A7 $\mathcal{D}'_m = \{x'_i\}_{i=1}^m$ is independent from the labeled inputs, $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$.

A6 states that the kernel density estimation is strongly uniformly consistent. Theorem A.3 guarantees that under certain technical conditions (see the Appendix), A6 holds. In this section, next to the norm estimation, the kernel density estimation is also a source of randomness, and A7 guarantees the independence between them.

Remark 7.1.1 If an unlabeled (“prototype”) sample is not available, the independence assumption in A7 can be achieved by using a portion of the inputs for the density estimation, and using the rest of the inputs for the norm estimation.

Let us introduce

$$a_{m,n} \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right),$$

where \wedge chooses the minimum between the two values and ρ is the (universal) constant from assumption A4. We will investigate this sequence and we aim to use the result of the Moore-Osgood theorem (see Appendix, Theorem A.7). The next observation states that if we write the values of the original density function instead the values of the kernel density estimation in the denominator, this term can be simplified, since A4 guarantees that $f_*(x)/h_*(x) \leq \rho$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

Observation 7.1.1

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)}$$

The next lemma examines the limit of the sequence $a_{m,n}$ if $m \rightarrow \infty$.

Lemma 7.1.1 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$, we have*

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} c_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)}$$

as $m \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof From A6, we have that $\hat{h}_m(x_i) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} h_*(x_i)$ for every $i \in [n]$, as $m \rightarrow \infty$. By using the Continuous Mapping Theorem (Appendix, Theorem A.11), it also follows, that $1/\hat{h}_m(x_i) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 1/h_*(x_i)$ holds for every $i \in [n]$. Let us fix the realization x_1, \dots, x_n . It holds true for every $i \in [n]$, that as $m \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) = \frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)},$$

since the \wedge operator is also continuous in the convergence. \square

Next, we will prove that the expected value of this term, while it is conditioned on the \mathcal{D}'_m dataset, equals to the kernel norm of the regression function.

Lemma 7.1.2 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$, it holds true that*

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \middle| \underbrace{x'_1, \dots, x'_m}_{\mathcal{D}'_m} \right] \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

as $m \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] = \\ & \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \leq \rho \right) \right) + \rho \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} > \rho \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Since the expected value is a linear operator, this term equals

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \leq \rho \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] + \rho \cdot \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} > \rho \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right).$$

For every $\rho' > \rho$, let us take the following value:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \leq \rho' \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] + \rho' \cdot \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} > \rho' \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right).$$

As $m \rightarrow \infty$, it holds true that

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} > \rho' \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 0, \quad \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \leq \rho' \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} 1.$$

Therefore, by using the Lebesgue Dominated Convergence Theorem and Lemma 7.1.1, we have, as $m \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

Let us define $\rho' \doteq \rho + 1/k$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and let Ω_k be the following event:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \leq \rho' \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] + \rho' \cdot \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} > \rho' \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

For the probability of Ω_k , we have $\mathbb{P}(\Omega_k) = 1$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore, we have

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcap_{k=1}^{\infty} \Omega_k \right) = 1,$$

which means that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \leq \rho \right) \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right] + \rho \cdot \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} > \rho \middle| \mathcal{D}'_m \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 7.1.3 *Assume A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. Let*

$$a_{m,n} \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right), \quad \text{and} \quad b_m \doteq \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x)}{\hat{h}_m(x)} \wedge \rho \right) h_*(x) \, dx.$$

Then, $\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists N(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n > N : \exists M(\varepsilon, n) : \forall m > M : |a_{m,n} - b_m| < \varepsilon$.

Proof We will prove, that for any $\varepsilon > 0$, it holds true, that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{m \rightarrow \infty} |a_{n,m} - b_m| < \varepsilon.$$

Let $\delta_m \doteq \sup_{m' \geq m} \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |\hat{h}_{m'}(x) - h_*(x)|$. By using A6, we can guarantee, that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \delta_m = 0$. We will provide a lower and upper bound for $a_{m,n}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \underbrace{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i) + \delta_m} \wedge \rho \right)}_{l_{m,n}} &\leq \underbrace{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right)}_{a_{m,n}} \leq \\ &\leq \underbrace{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i) - \delta_m} \cdot \mathbb{I}(h_*(x_i) - \delta_m > 0) \wedge \rho \right) + \mathbb{I}(h_*(x_i) - \delta_m \leq 0) \cdot \rho}_{u_{m,n}}. \end{aligned} \tag{7.1}$$

First, we examine $l_{m,n}$.

$$l_{m,n} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f_*^2(x)}{h_*(x)} h_*(x) \, dx = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

where first $m \rightarrow \infty$, then $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then, for $u_{m,n}$, we have

$$u_{m,n} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f_*^2(x)}{h_*(x)} h_*(x) dx = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

where first $m \rightarrow \infty$, then $n \rightarrow \infty$. □

Observation 7.1.2 *In the proof of Lemma 7.1.3, we have proven that*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{m \rightarrow \infty} |a_{n,m} - b_m| < \varepsilon.$$

The statement also holds true in the following form:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} |a_{n,m} - b_m| < \varepsilon.$$

This can be proven analogously, in addition to using the Lebesgue Dominated Convergence Theorem for the integral term, where $h_(x)dx \doteq d\mathbb{P}_x$.*

Next, we will prove a relaxed version of the Moore-Osgood Theorem [87], where the uniform convergence assumption is relaxed.

Theorem 7.1.4 (Relaxed Moore-Osgood Theorem) *If $\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists N(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n > N : \exists M(\varepsilon, n) : \forall m > M : |a_{n,m} - b_m| < \varepsilon$, and $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = c_n$ for each large n , then both $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} b_m$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} c_n$ exists and are equal to the double limit, namely*

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} a_{m,n}.$$

Proof For any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists an $N_1(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $n, k > N_1$ implies $|a_{n,m} - a_{n,k}| < \varepsilon/3$, where $m > M(\varepsilon)$, and $M(\varepsilon)$ is given by Lemma 7.1.3.

As $m \rightarrow \infty$, we have $|c_n - c_k| < \varepsilon/3$, therefore, c_n is a Cauchy sequence. Let L denote the limit of this sequence. If $k \rightarrow \infty$, then it follows, that $|c_n - L| < \varepsilon/3$.

If we take $k \rightarrow \infty$ first, then, for any $m > M(\varepsilon)$, we have $|a_{n,m} - b_m| < \varepsilon/3$.

By the pointwise convergence, for any $\varepsilon > 0$. and $n > N_1$, there exists an $N_2(n, \varepsilon)$, such that $m > N_2$ implies $|a_{n,m} - c_n| < \varepsilon/3$.

For any fixed $n, m > \max N_2, M$, we have the following inequality:

$$|b_m - L| \leq |b_m - a_{n,m}| + |a_{n,m} - c_n| + |c_n - L| \leq \varepsilon.$$

From this, it follows that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} b_m = L = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} c_n$. By taking $N \doteq \max\{N_1, N_2, M\}$,

$$L = \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} a_{m,n}.$$

□

From Lemma 7.1.1, Lemma 7.1.3 and Theorem 7.1.4, we can conclude our results.

Theorem 7.1.5 Assume A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. Then,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2\right) = 1.$$

Observation 7.1.3 In Chapter 6, we have provided finite sample guarantees for the reliability of the constructed confidence bands. The result provided by Theorem 7.1.5 is an asymptotic result.

Next, we will construct our estimation for providing a guaranteed upper bound for $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Lemma 7.1.6 Assume A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. Then, for any user-chosen risk probability $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_m) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

with the following choice on the upper bound κ :

$$\kappa_m \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right) + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n}}.$$

Proof First, we are going to prove, that the following convergence holds:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \right] \rightarrow \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

We can prove this by showing that this term is uniformly integrable. First, by using the properties of the expected value, we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) \right] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho \right].$$

It also holds true that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho \right] \leq \mathbb{E}[\rho] = \rho < \infty. \quad (7.2)$$

In order for this term to be uniformly integrable, the following must hold true:

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \sup_m \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho \right) \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho > K \right) \right] = 0. \quad (7.3)$$

By using (7.2), we obtain that

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \sup_m \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho \right) \cdot \mathbb{I} \left(\left(\frac{f_*^2(x_1)}{\hat{h}_m(x_1)} \wedge \rho \right) > K \right) \right] \leq \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \sup_m \mathbb{E} \left[\rho \cdot \mathbb{I}(\rho > K) \right] = 0,$$

which proves that (7.3) holds true.

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. In Lemma 7.1.1, we have proven that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\underbrace{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right)}_{a_{m,n}} \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} c_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_*^2(x_i)}{h_*(x_i)},$$

as $m \rightarrow \infty$. It holds true that $|a_{m,n}| \leq \rho$, and as $m \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\mathbb{E}[a_{m,n}] \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \mathbb{E}[c_n] = \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

From almost surely convergence, convergence in distribution follows. For every $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\mathbb{P}(a_{m,n} - \mathbb{E}[a_{m,n}] \geq \varepsilon) = \underbrace{\mathbb{P}(a_{m,n} \geq \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \varepsilon)}_{1 - F_{a_{m,n}}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \varepsilon)}.$$

As $m \rightarrow \infty$,

$$1 - F_{a_{m,n}}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \varepsilon) \rightarrow 1 - F_{c_n}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \varepsilon).$$

Therefore, by using Hoeffding's inequality, we have for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_*(x_i)^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_i)} \wedge \rho \right) - \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \geq \varepsilon \right) \leq \exp(-2n\varepsilon^2/\rho^2).$$

The rest of the proof is analogous to the proof of Lemma 6.1.1 using $R \doteq c_n$. \square

Observation 7.1.4 *Lemma 7.1.6 provides an asymptotic result with respect to the prototype sample, which is generally easier to obtain than the labeled data.*

By relaxing the assumption of the a priori knowledge of h_* , the core idea of the construction was not changed. We provide a short description of the method in this case.

Let us have any given input query point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, for which $x_0 \neq x_k$ for $k \in [n]$.

- (i) The Gram matrix is extended with x_0 , namely

$$K_0(i+1, j+1) \doteq k(x_i, x_j),$$

for $i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n$.

- (ii) We compute the highest and the lowest y_0 values which can be interpolated with a function from \mathcal{H} having at most norm square κ_m .
- (iii) This leads to the following *two* optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} \min / \max \quad & y_0 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & (y_0, y^T) K_0^{-1} (y_0, y^T)^T \leq \kappa_m \end{aligned} \tag{7.4}$$

where “min / max” means that we have to solve the problem as a minimization and also as a maximization (separately).

- (iv) The problems in (7.4) are convex, moreover, their solutions can be calculated analytically, which can be proven analogous to Section 6.1. The optimal values, denoted by y_{\min} and y_{\max} , respectively, determine the *endpoints* of the confidence interval for $f_*(x_0)$, that is $I_1(x_0) \doteq y_{\min}$ and $I_2(x_0) \doteq y_{\max}$. If there is no solution, we return $I(x_0) = \emptyset$.

The statistical guarantee is summarized in the the following theorem.

Theorem 7.1.7 *Assume A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$. For any risk probability $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the confidence band guarantees*

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \nu(\mathcal{I}_{m,n}) \geq 1 - \alpha.$$

Proof According to Lemma 7.1.6, we have

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_m) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

If $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_m$, then for all $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, for which $x_0 \neq x_k$ for $k \in [n]$, the value $f_*(x_0)$ is in the confidence band, since the function f_* interpolates the sample extended with $(x_0, f_*(x_0))$, and since $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_m$, the minimum norm interpolant of this extended sample inherits this norm bound. \square

Next, we will show that without the a priori knowledge of the h_* density function, the uniform strong consistency of the constructed confidence bands still holds. In order to prove this, we first have to prove that the norm estimation provided by Lemma 7.1.6 (almost surely) converges to $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$. This has been already stated in Theorem 7.1.5. In this case, the consistency holds for certain double-indexed sequences, as stated in the next theorem.

Theorem 7.1.8 *Assuming A1, A2, A4, A6, A7 and that $y_k = f_*(x_k)$ for $k \in [n]$, the constructed confidence bands, $\{\mathcal{C}_{m,n}\}$, are strongly uniformly consistent, in the following sense. For all double-indexed sequences $\{(m_i, n_i)\}$, where $\{m_i\}$ and $\{n_i\}$ are nondecreasing sequences of natural numbers, if $\min(m_i, n_i) \rightarrow \infty$, as $i \rightarrow \infty$, then we have*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{i=k}^{\infty} \{\mathcal{C}_{m_i, n_i} \subseteq B(f_*, \varepsilon)\}\right) = 1.$$

Proof The proof is mostly analogous to the construction in Section 6.1. The definition of the \hat{f}_n minimum norm interpolating function is unchanged. The set of functions \mathcal{C}_n and $\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_n$ now also depend on the parameter m as follows:

$$\mathcal{C}_{m,n} \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \ \& \ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa_m\},$$

By defining $\tilde{\kappa}_m \doteq \max\{\kappa_*, \kappa_m\}$,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{m,n} \doteq \{f \in \mathcal{H} : f \cong \mathcal{Z}_n \ \& \ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\kappa}_m\},$$

and the radius of the ball in Lemma 6.1.6 becomes $2\sqrt{(\tilde{\kappa}_m - \hat{\kappa}_m)}$. \square

Observation 7.1.5 *Without the a priori knowledge of h_* , the constructed confidence bands are still constructed separately for each input. By using the result of Theorem 6.1.4, and from the strong uniform consistency of our abstract confidence regions, the strong uniform consistency of the pointwise built confidence bands follows.*

7.2 Noisy Outputs

Next, we aim to generalize the previous result for a data with measurement noise, which satisfies A3. Let us define the following sequence:

$$a'_{m,n_0} \doteq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{M_{n,k}^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right),$$

where $M_{n,k}^2 = \max\{\nu_k^2, \mu_k^2\}$ from (6.8).

Theorem 7.2.1 *By assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6 and A7, it holds true that*

$$\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{M_{n,k}^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

as $m, n_0 \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof Assuming A5, for $\tilde{V}_n \doteq \max\{V_{n,1}, \dots, V_{n,n_0}\}$ and $\bar{V}_n \doteq \min\{V_{n,1}, \dots, V_{n,n_0}\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_n \underbrace{\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right)}_{a_{m,n_0}} &\leq \underbrace{\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{M_{n,k}^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right)}_{a'_{m,n_0}} = \\ \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_k) \cdot V_{n,k}}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right) &\leq \tilde{V}_n \underbrace{\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{f_*^2(x_k)}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right)}_{a_{m,n_0}}, \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to A5, both \bar{V}_n and \tilde{V}_n converge to 1 with probability 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$. If $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $n_0 \rightarrow \infty$ from (5.5). The rest of the proof follows from Theorem 7.1.5. \square

From this, we can construct the upper estimation to the kernel norm of the regression function, similarly to Lemma 7.1.6.

Lemma 7.2.2 *By assuming A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, for any user-chosen risk probabilities $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$, we have*

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau_m) \geq 1 - \alpha - \beta,$$

with the following choice on the upper bound κ :

$$\tau_m \doteq \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \left(\frac{M_{n,k}^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \wedge \rho \right) + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\alpha)}{2n_0}}.$$

The proof of this lemma follows from the proof of Lemma 7.2.2 and Theorem 7.2.1. By relaxing the assumption of the a priori knowledge of h_* , the core idea of the construction was not changed. We provide a short description of the method in this case. For any given input query point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, for which $x_0 \neq x_k$ for $k \in [n_0]$, we follow these steps:

- (i) The Gram matrix is extended with x_0 , namely

$$\tilde{K}_0(i+1, j+1) \doteq k(x_i, x_j),$$

for $i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n_0$.

- (ii) We solve the two following (convex) optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} \min / \max \quad & z_0 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0}) \tilde{K}_0^{-1}(z_0, \dots, z_{n_0})^T \leq \tau_m \\ & \nu_1 \leq z_1 \leq \mu_1, \dots, \nu_d \leq z_d \leq \mu_{n_0} \end{aligned} \tag{7.5}$$

where “min / max” again means that the problem have to be solved as a minimization and as a maximization (separately).

- (iii) The optimal values, denoted by z_{\min} and z_{\max} , are the *endpoints* of the confidence interval: $I_1(x_0) \doteq z_{\min}$, and $I_2(x_0) \doteq z_{\max}$. If (7.5) is infeasible, e.g., we get an empty KGP ellipsoid, we set $I(x_0) = \emptyset$.

Similarly to Section 6.2, we can once again provide a refined version of this algorithm. Since we no longer have a priori knowledge about the density function h_* , the primal task provided by (6.13) will have the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize} \quad & -\frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} \frac{z_k^2}{\hat{h}_m(x_k)} \\ \text{subject to} \quad & z \in \mathcal{Z} \end{aligned}$$

Instead of solving this problem, we can solve an equivalent form of the dual:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && \xi \\ & \text{subject to} && \rho \geq 0 \\ & && \begin{bmatrix} A_0 + \rho A_1 & \rho b_1 \\ \rho b_1^\top & \rho c_1 - \xi \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \end{aligned}$$

where $A_0 \doteq -\frac{1}{n_0} \text{diag}(1/\hat{h}_m(x_1), \dots, 1/\hat{h}_m(x_{n_0}))$, $A_1 \doteq K_2^{-1} H K_2^{-1}$, $b_1^\top \doteq -\hat{\theta}^\top H K_2^{-1}$, and $c_1 \doteq \hat{\theta}^\top H \hat{\theta} - 1$. If we denote the optimal solution by ξ^* , then the upper bound for $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$ is the following:

$$\tau_0 \doteq \xi^* + \rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\alpha)}{-2n_0}}.$$

The confidence bands will be constructed by solving the two following convex optimization problems:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min / \max && z_0 \\ & \text{subject to} && (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0}) K_0^{-1} (z_0, \dots, z_{n_0})^\top \leq \tau_0 \\ & && (z_1, \dots, z_{n_0}) \in \mathcal{Z}, \end{aligned} \tag{7.6}$$

The following theorem summarizes the guarantee of this construction.

Theorem 7.2.3 *Assume A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6 and A7. Let $\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$ be given risk probabilities. Then, for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$,*

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \nu(\mathcal{I}_{m,n}) \geq 1 - \alpha - \beta.$$

Proof Let us introduce the following event:

$$A \doteq \{(f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^\top \in \mathcal{Z} \wedge \|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau_0\}$$

According to Lemma 7.2.2, the event A has probability at least $1 - \alpha - \beta$ if $m, n \rightarrow \infty$.

Conditioning on event A , for all query input point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$ such that K_0 is invertible, which holds a.e., we can guarantee that there is a $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, namely $z = (f_*(x_1), \dots, f_*(x_{n_0}))^\top$, and z_0 , name $z_0 = f_*(x_0)$, such that the *minimum norm* interpolant of $\{(x_0, z_0)\} \cup \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0}$ has a norm square less or equal than τ_m , since f_* itself is an interpolant of this dataset. Thus, we have that $z_{\min} \leq z_0 \leq z_{\max}$, for $z_0 = f_*(x_0)$. This property is always guaranteed, hence, we *simultaneously* have for \mathbb{P}_X -a.e. $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d$ that $z_{\min}(x_0) \leq f_*(x_0) \leq z_{\max}(x_0)$, under A . \square

The strong uniform consistency will be proven similarly to the previous section. The consistency of the norm estimation is guaranteed by Theorem 7.2.1.

Theorem 7.2.4 *Assume A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6 and A7. Then, the constructed confidence bands, $\{\mathcal{D}_{m,n}\}$, are strongly uniformly consistent, in the following sense. For all double-indexed sequences $\{(m_i, n_i)\}$, where $\{m_i\}$ and $\{n_i\}$ are nondecreasing sequences of natural numbers, if $\min(m_i, n_i) \rightarrow \infty$, as $i \rightarrow \infty$, then we have*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{i=k}^{\infty} \{ \mathcal{D}_{m_i, n_i} \subseteq B(f_*, \varepsilon) \} \right) = 1.$$

Proof The proof is mostly analogous to the construction in Section 6.2. The definition of the $\hat{f}_{n,z}$ minimum norm interpolating function is unchanged. The set of functions \mathcal{D}_n and $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n$ now also depend on the parameter m as follows:

$$\mathcal{D}_{m,n} \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} : \exists z \in \mathcal{Z}_n : f \cong \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0} \wedge \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tau_m \}.$$

With the definition $\tilde{\tau}_m \doteq \max\{\tau_m, \kappa_*\}$,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{m,n} \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} : \exists z \in \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_n : f \cong \{(x_k, z_k)\}_{k=1}^{n_0} \wedge \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \tilde{\tau}_m \},$$

and the radius of the ball in Lemma 6.2.7 becomes $2\sqrt{\tilde{\tau}_m - (\bar{V} \wedge 1) \cdot \hat{\tau}_m}$. □

Observation 7.2.1 *We have proven strong uniform consistency for the norm term τ_m and the construction provided by the convex problems in (7.5). The result also follows for the improved tasks given by (7.6) from Lemma 6.2.4.*

Observation 7.2.2 *In the case of noisy outputs and unknown density h_* , the constructed confidence bands are still constructed separately for each input. By using the result of Theorem 6.1.4, and from the strong uniform consistency of our abstract confidence regions, the strong uniform consistency of the pointwise built confidence bands follows.*

Remark 7.2.1 *The Glivenko-Cantelli theorem states that the empirical distribution function converges uniformly to the original distribution function almost surely, which is also an asymptotical result [88]. The Dvoretzky–Kiefer–Wolfowitz inequality provides a quantitative result for the largest possible difference between the estimated and the original distribution function value for finite sample cases [89]. This result is not directly applicable for the kernel density estimation approach, however, a non-asymptotic result could be achieved by using this method.*

Figure 7.1: Simultaneous confidence bands, having coverage probabilities 10 %, 50 % and 90 %, for unknown input distribution and noise-free outputs.

7.3 Numerical Experiments

These algorithms were also implemented and tested numerically. The original data-generating function was generated similarly then in Section 6.4.

Once we no longer assumed the a priori knowledge of the input distribution, we used the KDE method to estimate the unknown h_* density function behind the inputs. We used a Gaussian kernel with parameter $\sigma = 1$ and the bandwidth was $b = n^{-1/6}$. $n = 40$ noise-free observations was generated from f_* . The inputs $\{x_k\}$ followed Laplace distribution with location $\mu = 0$ and scale $b = 0.8$. The parameter for the Paley-Wiener RKHS was $\eta = 30$. Figure 7.1 shows that even in the case of unknown input distribution, the method provides informative confidence bands for the regression function.

We are adding a non-symmetric noise term to the outputs with the distribution $\{\varepsilon_k\}$ noise terms was $\varepsilon \sim \exp(\lambda) - \lambda$ for $\lambda = 0.3$. The inputs followed Laplace distribution with location $\mu = 0$ and scale $b = 0.5$. The parameter of the Paley-Wiener RKHS was $\eta = 20$. Figure 7.2 shows that even with noisy outputs and an unknown input distribution, the confidence bands lead to informative and adequate simultaneous confidence bands.

Figure 7.2: Simultaneous confidence bands, having coverage probabilities 10 %, 50 % and 90 %, for unknown input distributions and noisy outputs (unknown distribution).

Chapter 8

Single Image Inpainting and Super-Resolution with Uncertainty Bounds

In this chapter, we demonstrate the practical applicability of our ideas by studying single image restoration and super-resolution problems. Next to the estimation of the unknown pixel values, we will also be able to construct guaranteed uncertainty bounds.

8.1 Introduction

The task of *image restoration* is to create a higher quality image from a lower quality measurement. There are many examples for lack of quality, including missing, damaged pixels due to noise, blur, or compression [90, 91]. In many cases the degradation of such images is irreversible, which makes this task very challenging in many cases. If the task is based on one image without any additional information, then the problem is called *single image restoration*; and when the objective is to estimate the values of missing pixels, it is called *single image inpainting* [92]. There are several methods for these problems, from total variation based techniques to methods using biharmonic equations [93], and recently *deep learning* approaches also became popular [94, 95].

A closely related task is the so-called *single image super-resolution*, which aims to create a higher resolution image from a lower resolution one [96]. A wide range of super-resolution methods have been developed over the years, from bicubic interpolation to Lanczos resampling, but recent approaches implementing *deep learning*, such as generative adversarial network (GAN) or convolutional network based methods, produce the state-of-the-art results [97, 98]. On the other hand, most of the available methods do not come with strict theoretical and uncertainty guarantees. They generally do not provide information about how accurate their pixel estimates are, they do not quantify the uncertainty of their outcomes.

We propose an approach, called *Simultaneously Guaranteed Kernel Interpolation* (SGKI), to single image inpainting and super-resolution problems that not only provides estimates for the unknown pixel values, but it also constructs *non-asymptotic, non-parametric confidence regions* which are *simultaneously guaranteed* for all missing pixels. The core idea builds on the minimum norm interpolants in RKHSs. The existence and the uniqueness of this function is provided by Theorem 3.8.1.

8.2 Universal Kernels

In Chapter 3, we have defined RKHSs. An important question when choosing kernels is that what kind of functions can be represented or approximated by linear combinations of the chosen kernel.

Definition 8.2.1 (Universal Kernels) *Let \mathbb{X} be a metric space, let $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ be a compact subset and let $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a kernel, i.e., symmetric and positive definite. Let $\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{Z}) \doteq \overline{\text{span}}\{k(z, \cdot) : z \in \mathcal{Z}\}$, i.e., the set of all functions which are uniform limits of linear combinations of $k(z, \cdot)$, with $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, functions. Let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{Z})$ be the set of all continuous $f : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ type function. Kernel k is called universal if and only if for all compact $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{X}$, we have $\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{Z}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{Z})$.*

In other words, linear combinations of universal kernels can approximate arbitrary well (in the supremum norm) continuous functions on any compact set, that is, they have the *universal approximating property* [99].

A kernel $k : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called *translation invariant*, if there is a function $\psi : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{X} : k(x, y) = \psi(x - y)$. Let \mathbb{X} be a metric space (this allows us to talk about the continuity and integrability of the kernels, as we can use the Borel σ -algebra induced by the metric of the space). It is known that bounded, continuous, integrable, translation invariant, strictly positive definite kernels are universal [100]. Based on this, both the Gaussian and the Paley-Wiener kernel are universal. It will also be important for us that continuous, universal kernels are strictly positive definite [100], consequently, their Gram matrices are invertible for distinct inputs.

8.3 Problem Setting

We treat images as functions having $d = 2$ dimensional input vectors. The pixels are outputs of these functions at some observed inputs, typically distributed on a grid, for example, corresponding to the array of photosites of a digital camera. For simplicity, we assume that the inputs come from $\mathcal{D} \doteq [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, and first we assume that the

outputs are scalars, hence we have *grayscale* images. More precisely, the pixel intensities are *centered* and *scaled*, thus they are from $[-1, 1]$.

The extension of this approach for multi-dimensional outputs will be also discussed, for example, to the case when the pixel values are from $[-1, 1]^m$ describing RGB (red, green, blue) or CMYK (cyan, magenta, yellow, key / black) color codes. Our fundamental assumptions on the available data can be summarized as

B1 We have a finite sample, $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$, where $x_k \in \mathcal{D} \doteq [0, 1]^d$, $y_k \in [-1, 1]$, and, $y_k = f_*(x_k)$, for $k \in [n]$. We assume that the inputs $\{x_k\}$ are distinct, formally, $\forall i, j \in [n] : i \neq j \Rightarrow x_i \neq x_j$ and that f_* belongs to a known RKHS \mathcal{H} with a continuous and universal kernel k .

Remark 8.3.1 The current version of the method assumes that the underlying true data generation function can be observed perfectly at the sample inputs. Therefore, we disregard observation noises including output quantization. We do so to simplify the presentation, but the method can be extended to the case of observation noises, as shown in [74, 101, 50].

Our two main goals are (1) to estimate the missing pixel value of any given (out of sample) query input point, as well as (2) to provide uncertainty bounds for our estimates. Albeit, there are several solutions to (1), but most of them do not come with uncertainty guarantees: they do not address (2).

Formally, the goals are to construct a *point estimate* \bar{f} of f_* together with a *confidence band*, i.e., a function $I : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, such that $I(x) = (I_1(x), I_2(x))$ specifies the *endpoints* of an interval estimate for $f_*(x)$ and contains $\bar{f}(x)$, for any $x \in \mathcal{D}$. Hence, based on our dataset $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, we need to construct function \bar{f} and band I with

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \mathcal{D} : \quad & \bar{f}(x) \in [I_1(x), I_2(x)], \\ \nu(I) \doteq & \mathbb{P}(\forall x \in \mathcal{D} : I_1(x) \leq f_*(x) \leq I_2(x)) \geq 1 - \gamma, \end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ is a user-chosen *risk* probability, and $\nu(I)$ is the *reliability* (coverage probability) of the confidence band.

8.4 Confidence Bands with Known Norm Bounds

In this section, we describe the algorithm which constructs the *point estimates* with the corresponding *confidence intervals* for each query input. Then, the algorithm can be applied to estimate the intensities of missing pixels, or to construct a higher resolution image by estimating the function values on a refined grid. We apply the construction discussed in Section 6.1 to image reconstruction.

Remark 8.4.1 *Our approach has similarities with the classical Wiener filter method [93] in image reconstruction, e.g., both concern with \mathcal{L}^2 model fitting. However, (i) our algorithm builds on interpolation instead of regression, (ii) our method is nonparametric, and most importantly, the main advantage of our approach is that (iii) it provides non-asymptotically guaranteed confidence regions for the true values, which are also distribution-free (unlike, e.g., Gaussian process regression).*

In this section, we make the simplifying assumption that a priori known bounds are available for the kernel norm of the data generating function. Later, in Section 8.5, we will discuss how to estimate these bounds based on the image itself, assuming that the data generating function is band-limited, i.e., it is from a Paley-Wiener space.

We start with constructing the point estimate \bar{f} . Recall, that the element from \mathcal{H} which *interpolates* every y_k at the corresponding x_k and has the *smallest norm* among such interpolants, that is

$$\bar{f} \doteq \arg \min \{ \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}} \mid f \in \mathcal{H} \ \& \ \forall k \in [n] : f(x_k) = y_k \},$$

exists and for every input x , it takes the following form:

$$\bar{f}(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n \hat{\alpha}_k k(x, x_k), \tag{8.1}$$

where the weights are $\hat{\alpha} = K^{-1}y$ with $y \doteq (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T$ and $\hat{\alpha} \doteq (\hat{\alpha}_1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_n)$, and $K_{i,j} = k(x_i, x_j)$ is the Gram matrix. Since the kernel is continuous and universal by assumption B1, it is strictly positive definite. Moreover, we also assumed that the inputs $\{x_k\}$ are distinct (which can be interpreted as there are no duplicated pixel intensities), therefore, matrix K is always invertible in our case.

Remark 8.4.2 *The main reason why we use (8.1) as our function estimate is that the kernel norm in an RKHS acts as a Lipschitz-style smoothness measure [27], hence, we choose the “smoothest” possible function which is consistent with our observations.*

For the confidence region construction, we first make the following simplifying (auxiliary) assumption that stochastically guaranteed bounds are available for the kernel norm:

B2 *Given $\gamma \in (0,1)$, we know a constant $\kappa \geq \|\bar{f}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$ with*

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa) \geq 1 - \gamma.$$

A natural question which arises is that where can such bounds come from? In the context of image processing, if we are working with specific kinds of images (such as x-ray or satellite images), we could compute the kernel norms of a large number of such

images and then construct κ based on the *empirical quantiles* of these norms. For example, if we have the norms of 1000 images and $\gamma = 0.05$, then κ can be the smallest number such that it is larger than the norms of at least 950 images. Alternatively, we can try to build an *upper confidence bound* of the kernel norm based on the image itself. In Section 8.5 we will follow this latter idea, assuming that the data generating function is band-limited as well as the inputs are independent and uniformly distributed.

The main idea of algorithm is the same as method described in Chapter 6. For a query input $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$, we have to calculate the highest and lowest y_0 values, which can be interpolated with a function from \mathcal{H} having at most norm square κ . This leads to the following two tasks:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min / \max \quad y_0 \\ & \text{subject to} \quad (y_0, y^T) K_0^{-1} (y_0, y^T)^T \leq \kappa, \end{aligned} \tag{8.2}$$

where “min / max” means that we have to solve the problem as a minimization and also as a maximization (separately). The problems given in (8.2) are convex, they are always feasible under B1 and B2, furthermore, they have *analytic* solutions discussed in Section 6.1. By denoting the optimal values by y_{\min} and y_{\max} , respectively, the endpoints of the confidence interval for $f_*(x_0)$ are given by $I_1(x_0) \doteq y_{\min}$ and $I_2(x_0) \doteq y_{\max}$.

The pseudocode of the method, called *Simultaneously Guaranteed Kernel Interpolation* (SGKI), is given by Algorithm 4.

The SGKI method builds simultaneously guaranteed confidence bands, that is

Theorem 8.4.1 *Assuming B1 and B2, for any risk probability $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ and any finite sample size n , the SGKI confidence band is guaranteed to have reliability $\nu(I) \geq 1 - \gamma$.*

Next, we also show that our estimate (the minimum norm interpolant) is always included in the constructed region:

Lemma 8.4.2 *If B1, B2, then $\forall x \in \mathcal{D} : \bar{f}(x) \in [(I_1(x), I_2(x))]$.*

Proof Let us fix a query input $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$. If there is a $k \in [n]$, such that $x_0 = x_k$, then the statement trivially holds.

Now assume that $x_0 \neq x_k$ for all $k \in [n]$. Let us introduce:

$$\mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} \mid \forall k \in [n] : f(x_k) = y_k, f(x_0) = y, \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa \},$$

which contains those interpolants of the extended dataset that has a norm square less than or equal to our upper bound κ .

We can observe that $\bar{f} \in \mathcal{G}_{\bar{f}(x_0)}^\kappa$, since $\kappa \geq \|\bar{f}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$. Then,

$$I_1(x_0) = \min_{y: \mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \neq \emptyset} y \leq \bar{f}(x_0) \leq \max_{y: \mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \neq \emptyset} y = I_2(x_0),$$

Algorithm 4 Simultaneously Guaranteed Kernel Interpolation (SGKI)

Input: dataset of observed pixels, $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$,
 input query point $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$, upper bound κ for $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

Output: point estimate $\bar{f}(x_0)$ for the pixel value $f_*(x_0)$
 together with a confidence interval $[I_1(x_0), I_2(x_0)]$.

- 1: In case $x_0 = x_k$ for any $k \in [n]$, return $\bar{f}(x_0) = y_k$ with uncertainty bounds $I_1(x_0) = I_2(x_0) = y_k$. Otherwise:
- 2: Calculate the minimum norm interpolant at x_0 :

$$\bar{f}(x_0) = \sum_{k=1}^n \hat{\alpha}_k k(x_0, x_k),$$

where the weights are $\hat{\alpha} = K^{-1}y$ with $y \doteq (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T$

- 3: Create the extended Gram matrix: for $i, j = 0, \dots, n$ let

$$K_0(i+1, j+1) \doteq k(x_i, x_j).$$

- 4: Compute K_0^{-1} according to (6.19) and partition it as

$$\begin{bmatrix} c & b^T \\ b & A \end{bmatrix} \doteq K_0^{-1}.$$

- 5: For $a_0 \doteq c, b_0 \doteq 2b^T y, c_0 \doteq y^T A y - (n+1) \cdot \kappa$, solve the quadratic equation $a_0 y_0^2 + b_0 y_0 + c_0 = 0$.
 - 6: Return $\bar{f}(x_0)$ with $I_1(x_0) \doteq y_{\min}$, and $I_2(x_0) \doteq y_{\max}$, where $y_{\min} \leq y_{\max}$ are the two solutions of the quadratic equation above (they exist, but they can coincide).
-

which proves the statement, as $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$ was arbitrary. \square

Besides the *non-asymptotic* coverage guarantee, we should also show that the estimate (minimum norm interpolant) is always included in the confidence band:

Lemma 8.4.3 *If B1, B2, then $\forall x \in \mathcal{D} : \bar{f}(x) \in [(I_1(x), I_2(x))]$.*

Proof Let us fix a query input $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$. If there is a $k \in [n]$, such that $x_0 = x_k$, then the statement trivially holds. Now assume that $x_0 \neq x_k$ for all $k \in [n]$. Let us introduce:

$$\mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \doteq \{ f \in \mathcal{H} \mid \forall k \in [n] : f(x_k) = y_k, f(x_0) = y, \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa \},$$

which contains those interpolants of the extended dataset that has a norm square less than or equal to our upper bound κ . We can observe that $\bar{f} \in \mathcal{G}_{\bar{f}(x_0)}^\kappa$, since $\kappa \geq \|\bar{f}\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$. Then,

$$I_1(x_0) = \min_{y: \mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \neq \emptyset} y \leq \bar{f}(x_0) \leq \max_{y: \mathcal{G}_y^\kappa \neq \emptyset} y = I_2(x_0),$$

which proves the statement of the lemma, as the query input $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$ was arbitrary. \square

Remark 8.4.3 *The confidence interval construction of Algorithm 1 could also be used together with other image restoration methods, since it provides a general approach for uncertainty quantification, even without \bar{f} .*

The standard form of SGKI works with grayscale images, as we assume that f_* is scalar-valued. In case of color images, the pixels are given by multiple numbers, e.g., by RGB or CMY codes. In this case, $f_* : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow [-1, 1]^m$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$, typically $m = 3$ or $m = 4$. Thus we have vector-valued outputs. The simplest way to handle this issue is to estimate the true value of each coordinate separately. Then, for each query input $x_0 \in \mathcal{D}$ we have a confidence interval for each possible coordinate. These intervals can be combined into a hyperrectangle to get a confidence region for $f_*(x_0)$.

8.5 Bound for the Kernel Norm

In this section, we address the problem of computing κ , i.e. we are constructing a stochastic upper bound of $\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$ from the image, to get rid of B2. In order to do so, we introduce three new assumptions.

B3 Function f_* is from a Paley-Wiener space \mathcal{H} ; and f_* is almost time-limited to \mathcal{D} , i.e.,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} f_*^2(x) \mathbb{I}(x \notin \mathcal{D}) \lambda(dx) \leq \delta_0,$$

where $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is an indicator and $\delta_0 > 0$ is a universal constant.

Because of the *Fourier uncertainty principle*, we must allow the “true” function to be defined outside of \mathcal{D} , but this part of f_* should be “negligible”, i.e., its norm cannot exceed a (known) small constant, δ_0 .

B4 Sample $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n) \in \mathcal{D} \times \mathbb{R}$ is i.i.d.

B5 The inputs, $\{x_k\}$, are distributed uniformly on \mathcal{D} .

Recall, that the construction of κ was given in Lemma 6.1.1. Since B5 guarantees uniform assumption behind the inputs, we have

Lemma 8.5.1 *Assuming B3, B4, B5, for any $\gamma \in (0, 1)$, we have*

$$\mathbb{P}(\|f_*\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \leq \kappa) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

with the following upper bound:

$$\kappa \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n y_k^2 + \sqrt{\frac{\ln(\gamma)}{-2n}} + \delta_0. \tag{8.3}$$

Remark 8.5.1 *Since Assumption B5 guarantees that the inputs have uniform distribution on \mathcal{D} , the Proof of Lemma 8.5.1 can be used to prove the result of Lemma 6.1.1.*

In image reconstruction we often work with quantized inputs, i.e., f_* cannot be queried at arbitrary points, but there is a lattice structure $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^r$ induced by the points of a sampling grid $\{\bar{x}_i\}_{i=1}^r$, where r is the spatial resolution [93]. We can extend the result of Lemma 8.5.1 by taking into account the quantization error of inputs in (8.3), namely, by using $\kappa_r \doteq \kappa + \delta_r$, where

$$\delta_r \doteq \max_{i \in [r]} \sup_{x \in A_i} |f_*^2(\bar{x}_i) - f_*^2(x)|,$$

assuming this local Lipschitz constant, or an upper bound of it, is known. Fortunately, δ_r typically becomes negligible as the resolution increases and the sampling approaches the Nyquist rate [93]. Therefore, we can typically assume that we sample the pixels themselves using a discrete uniform distribution.

8.6 Numerical Experiments

In this section we present a series of numerical experiments with the proposed method, to demonstrate its performance. We have investigated both *synthetic* (artificially generated) and *real-world images* and studied both *inpainting* and *super-resolution* problems. One of the main drawbacks of simultaneously guaranteed kernel interpolation (SGKI) is its non-asymptotic uncertainty quantification (UQ), but since most image processing methods do not offer UQ, it is hard to fairly compare SGKI with other methods, apart from only using \bar{f} , the associated SGKI point estimate.

For *quantitative* comparisons, we used three quality metrics which we now introduce for the sake of completeness. They measure specific “distances” between the original image and the reconstructed one. Let us start by recalling the standard *mean squared error* (MSE) criterion for matrices $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w}$, where h and w denote the height and the width of the matrix (e.g., encoding a grayscale image), respectively:

$$\text{MSE}(A, B) \doteq \frac{1}{hw} \|A - B\|_{\mathbb{F}}^2 = \frac{1}{hw} \sum_{i=1}^h \sum_{j=1}^w (A_{i,j} - B_{i,j})^2,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{F}}$ denotes the *Frobenius norm*. The three *quality metrics* were as follows.

- *Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio* (PSNR) is often defined in signal processing as the logarithm of the ratio between the “power” of the noise (typically using the decibel scale) and the maximum possible “power” of the signal. In our case, it is defined as

$$\text{PSNR}(A, B) \doteq 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{M^2}{\text{MSE}(A, B)} \right),$$

where M is the maximum pixel value (e.g., for grayscale images it is usually 255).

- *Structural Similarity Index Measure* (SSIM) quantifies the similarity between two images by taking several parameters into account, such as contrast, brightness and structure [102]. Its formula is given by

$$\text{SSIM}(A, B) \doteq \frac{(2\mu_A\mu_B + c_1)(2\sigma_{AB} + c_2)}{(\mu_A^2 + \mu_B^2 + c_1)(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2 + c_2)},$$

where μ_A and μ_B denote the sample mean, σ_A^2 and σ_B^2 are the (empirical) variances, σ_{AB} is the (empirical) covariance of the pixels for images A and B and $c_1 \doteq (k_1L)^2$, $c_2 \doteq (k_2L)^2$ are variables, which stabilize the division. L is the dynamic range of the pixel values, while $k_1 = 0.01$ and $k_2 = 0.03$ are constant parameters.

- *Normalized Root Mean Square Error* (NRMSE) is a normalized version of the root of the mean squared error (RMSE). In our case, we used the following normalization

$$\text{NRMSE}(A, B) \doteq \frac{\sqrt{\text{MSE}(A, B)} \cdot \sqrt{hw}}{\|A\|_{\text{F}}} = \frac{\|A - B\|_{\text{F}}}{\|A\|_{\text{F}}},$$

where A plays the role of the original “true” image and B is the reconstructed one.

We start by presenting our experiments on *synthetic* test images. We generated 100 images based on data generating functions that were guaranteed to be contained in our chosen \mathcal{H} . We used a Paley-Wiener RKHS with parameter $\eta = 50$ and the “true” function was constructed as follows: 20 random $\bar{x}_k \in [0, 1]^2$; $k \in [20]$ knot points were generated with uniform $[0, 1]$ distribution on both of their coordinates. Then $f_*(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{20} w_k k(x, \bar{x}_k)$ was created, where each w_k had a uniform distribution on $[-1, 1]$. The obtained function was normalized, in case its maximum exceeded 1. The resolution of the images was $r \times r$ with $r = 50$. For the pixel at position (i, j) , where $i, j \in [50]$, we have $y_{i,j} \doteq f_*(x_k)$, if pixel (i, j) is observed and its input vector (i.e., on the sampling grid) is $x_k \in \mathcal{D} \doteq [0, 1]^2$; e.g., $x_{k,1} = i/(r + 1)$ and $x_{k,2} = j/(r + 1)$.

For the single image inpainting problem, just (random) 10 % of the pixels of the generated images were observed. The interpolant of SGKI, with the PW kernel, was compared with three different methods: *Total Variation* [103], which estimates the values of the missing pixels by minimizing the total variation subject to the matching known pixel values; an algorithm utilizing the *biharmonic equation* [104]; and *Large Mask Inpainting* [105], which uses fast Fourier convolutions. The results of the quantitative experiments are summarized in Table 8.1, where the averages of PSNR, SSIM and NRMSE are shown.

Note that for the PSNR and the SSIM quality metrics, higher values indicate better reconstruction performance, while for NRMSE, lower values are preferred.

Table 8.1: Synthetic single image inpainting experiments using 100 randomly generated “band-limited” images with 10 % observations.

Inpainting	PSNR (avg)	SSIM (avg)	NRMSE (avg)
SGKI-PW	26.0489	0.7499	0.1082
Total Variation	23.3874	0.5354	0.1356
Biharmonic	25.4460	0.6872	0.1074
Large Mask	22.6320	0.4711	0.1476

This experiment shows that if the characteristics of the image fit perfectly our *inductive hypothesis*, induced by our kernel choice (which was ensured by our image generation process), then SGKI provides an excellent performance and outperforms standard, widespread inpainting methods (w.r.t. the PSNR and SSIM metrics; for NRMSE, the biharmonic approach was slightly, but not significantly better).

We also investigated how *robust* the SGKI method is w.r.t. misspecified model classes. In order to test this, we used the same 100 synthetic images as before with random 10 % of the pixels as inputs. We had $\eta_* = 50$, while we used other η (hyper-parameter) values for our PW kernel. Recall that η_* specifies the bound on the allowed frequencies of the underlying “true” data-generating function. The resulting (averaged) quality metrics (y -axis) depending on the chosen kernel hyper-parameter (x -axis) are shown in Figure 8.1. The results demonstrate that choosing too low η values (i.e., lower than the true frequency bound) could result in significant performance losses, but SGKI is much more robust against over-bounding the frequencies, as increasing η above the “true” $\eta_* = 50$ typically only results in very modest performance losses.

Figures 8.2 and 8.3 illustrate the visual quality of the obtained results. Specifically, for Figure 8.3 non-random observations were used, as a filled circle shape was cut out from the image. In this latter case, the Large Mask approach (PSNR: 24.9824, SSIM: 0.6298, NRMSE: 0.1122) performed similarly to SGKI (PSNR: 25.0751, SSIM: 0.6747, NRMSE: 0.1110). On the other hand, Large Mask provided a poor result for the case of random observations, for which the Biharmonic method had similar performance to SGKI. Conversely, the Biharmonic method did a poorer job for a large cut-out. In conclusion, for synthetic images (for which we can guarantee that our assumptions are satisfied), SGKI provided the most stable results for the inpainting problem.

Regarding the *super-resolution* problem, 20 synthetic images were generated using the same method as before. A Paley-Wiener RKHS was used with parameter $\eta = 50$. The

Figure 8.1: Synthetic single image inpainting experiment, with 10% of the pixels observed, about the robustness of model class selection. The x -axis represents the different η (hyper-parameter) values of the applied Paley-Wiener kernel, while the y -axis shows the respective (averaged) values of the three image quality metrics (PSNR was normalized by its highest realization, in order to get its values in $[0, 1]$). The synthetic images were generated with the “true” value $\eta_* = 50$, which is marked by a gray dashed line.

Figure 8.2: Synthetic single image inpainting experiment; random 10% observed pixels.

resolution of the images was $2r \times 2r$ with $r = 50$, which was reduced to $r \times r$ pixels by using *subsampling*, namely, every second pixel in every second row (hence, 1 out of 4 pixels) was chosen to create an image with resolution $r \times r$. These reduced images were used as inputs for the tested super-resolution methods, and the reconstructed images

Figure 8.3: Synthetic single image inpainting experiment with a large, deterministic cut-out: instead of random pixels, a circle was removed. In this case, 1244 from the 2500 the pixels were observed.

were then compared with the original ones based on our quality metrics.

SGKI was also compared with other methods in this case: two state-of-the-art approaches based on deep learning, namely *Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution (EDSR)* [106], and *Multi-Scale Residual Network (MSRN)* [107]. Next to that, we have used several other methods in the comparison, as well, which provide their estimates based on nearby pixel value(s): *Bicubic Interpolation* [108], which uses the 4×4 neighborhood, and *Bilinear Interpolation* [109], which uses a 2×2 neighborhood while determining the value of a new pixel. The *Nearest-Neighbor Interpolation* [110] uses the value of the nearest pixel. Meanwhile, the *Lanczos Resampling* [111], which is based on the *sinc* function, uses a 8×8 neighborhood (in our case) for estimation. All tested super-resolution methods were used with a $\times 2$ scale. The quantitative results are summarized in Table 8.2.

It can be observed that for experiments with synthetic data, in which the images were generated in a way that they were guaranteed to satisfy our assumptions, the SGKI method provided the best results even for the super-resolution problem.

We have studied the kernel weights of the minimum norm interpolant, as well. Recall that this interpolant, shown in Algorithm 1, is our point estimate of the missing pixels. We have generated a synthetic image, removed some parts of it, and plotted the kernel weights, $\{\hat{\alpha}_k\}$, to demonstrate the impacts of the observed pixels. The weights were first rescaled to the interval $[-1, 1]$, then for each weight $\hat{\alpha}_k$, we plotted $\hat{\alpha}_k^p$ with $p = 0.25$. We

Figure 8.4: Kernel weights in an inpainting problem for a synthetic image (red: positive, blue: negative).

Table 8.2: Synthetic single image super-resolution experiments using 20 “band-limited” images with the aim to double their resolution.

Super-resolution	PSNR (avg)	SSIM (avg)	NRMSE (avg)
SGKI-PW	38.1143	0.9831	0.0258
EDSR	36.1177	0.9741	0.0311
MSRN	36.1017	0.9740	0.0312
Bicubic	35.9471	0.9734	0.0318
Bilinear	35.8641	0.9725	0.0321
Lanczos	36.0334	0.9745	0.0315
Nearest Neighbor	33.2433	0.9447	0.0433

did this last step to enhance the visibility of weights closer to zero. Figure 8.4 illustrates the weights for a synthetic inpainting problem. This experiment demonstrates which pixels or patterns are more “informative” with respect to the image we are processing. Note that only the available (actually observed) pixels have weights.

We now present our experiments on *real-world* images. Quantitative experiments were also performed for both problems on the (rescaled) *Set12* dataset [112], which consists 12 grayscale images with resolution 256×256 . The photos show people, animals, vegetables, houses and vehicles.

For the single image inpainting task, the images were rescaled by using Bicubic interpolation. In this case, SGKI was used with the Gaussian kernel with parameter $\sigma = 0.05$; recall that this kernel is defined as $k(z, s) \doteq \exp(-\|z - s\|^2 / (2\sigma^2))$.

For the inpainting problem, 10 separate experiments were performed for each image in

Table 8.3: Single image inpainting experiments, with 10 % pixels observed, on real-world images from the grayscale Set12 dataset.

Inpainting	PSNR (avg)	SSIM (avg)	NRMSE (avg)
SGKI-G	16.7601	0.3792	0.2765
Total Variation	17.0084	0.4201	0.2693
Biharmonic	17.3096	0.5260	0.2605
Large Mask	14.7450	0.2237	0.3477

Table 8.4: Single image super-resolution experiments on real-world images from the grayscale Set12 dataset; the target scale was $\times 4$.

Super-resolution	PSNR (avg)	SSIM (avg)	NRMSE (avg)
SGKI-PW	21.6117	0.6263	0.1597
EDSR	16.7301	0.5049	0.2773
MSRN	16.8671	0.5078	0.2729
Bicubic	19.9679	0.6119	0.1911
Bilinear	20.4913	0.6211	0.1801
Lanczos	19.8083	0.5967	0.1946
Nearest Neighbor	18.8881	0.5624	0.2166

the dataset, with (random) 10 % of the pixels observed. For the super-resolution problem, we again applied subsampling, but now every fourth pixel in every fourth row (thus, 1 out of 16 pixels) was chosen to create the rescaled images. For this task, the Paley-Wiener kernel was applied with parameter $\eta = 175$ and the super-resolution algorithms were used with scale $\times 4$. The results are summarized in Tables 8.3 and 8.4.

The SGKI method, with the Gaussian kernel, provided solid results for the inpainting problem on this dataset, though the Total Variation and the Biharmonic methods were slightly better. On the other hand, SGKI with a PW kernel showed excellent results for the super-resolution problem, it achieved even better results than EDSR and MSRN. We emphasize that we applied subsampling to obtain the lower resolution images, as this technique ensured the setup we assumed regarding the observations.

As a visual illustration of inpainting, Figure 8.5 shows an experiment, where the

original picture¹ had resolution 50×50 and only 1250 pixels were observed from the total 2500. Here, the Gaussian kernel was used with (hyper-) parameter $\sigma = 0.03$.

Figure 8.5: Visual comparison of single image inpainting methods; 50% observed pixels.

Remark 8.6.1 *The Nearest Neighbor (NN) method was not plotted in Figure 8.6, since its output does not differ from the observed image except from its resolution.*

Figure 8.6 presents a visual illustration for super-resolution methods. In this experiment, an image with $4r \times 4r = 200 \times 200$ pixels was used, which was reduced to $r \times r$ pixels ($r = 50$) with subsampling, as before, selecting 1 out of 16 pixels to be kept. In the SGKI case, the Paley-Wiener kernel was applied with parameter $\eta = 175$.

It is important to note that the results regarding SGKI only show the minimum norm interpolant, \bar{f} , which is basically the center of the confidence band. However, one does not need to use this interpolant, the UQ of SGKI can be combined with other methods to evaluate their uncertainty. The simultaneous SGKI confidence bands are guaranteed irrespectively of the actual method used to estimate the missing pixels.

Finally, our last experiment illustrates that SGKI can be applied for *color* images, as well, and it also illustrates the resulting confidence bands. Figure 8.7 presents an experiment for *image inpainting* on a 50×50 color image together with the accompanied UQ regions. In this case 2250 from the 2500 pixels were observed, then the missing pixels were estimated with the minimum norm (PW) interpolant. SGKI was used with the

¹All of the real-world photos presented were obtained from Pixabay, they were also edited.

Figure 8.6: Visual comparison of single image super-resolution methods; target scale: $\times 4$.

Figure 8.7: Single image inpainting and uncertainty quantification; 90% observed pixels.

Paley-Wiener kernel with parameters $\eta = 50$ and $\gamma = 0.1$ (i.e., the confidence band had coverage probability 90%). For a scalar output, the size of the uncertainty for query input x_0 can be defined as $|I_1(x_0) - I_2(x_0)|$. To help the visualization, a relative quantity was used: let us denote the largest uncertainty value by U_{\max} , then for an arbitrary $x_0 \neq x_k$, $k \in [n]$, the relative uncertainty was defined as $1 - (|I_1(x_0) - I_2(x_0)|/U_{\max})^{1/4}$. These values were combined in the vector-valued (RGB) case by using the luminance weights: 0.3 (R), 0.59 (G) and 0.11 (B).

Conclusions

In this thesis, a nonparametric and distribution-free method was proposed to construct simultaneous confidence bands for band-limited functions, which problem is especially crucial for statistical signal processing. First, the problem setting with the main assumptions was presented, then, as a preliminary result, we provided a confidence band construction for the case of finite-dimensional model classes. Then, with the help of the recently developed KGP method, we were able to create simultaneous confidence intervals for a subset of the (observed) sample inputs for the general (nonparametric) case.

The main construction, which is able to generalize to out-of-sample inputs, was first presented with the assumption of having a priori knowledge of the distribution function behind the inputs. Initially, we further simplified the task by assuming that there are also no measurement noises. For this case, we suggested a method that can be computed analytically for each query input. Then, the construction was extended for the case of also having measurement noises, which are independent from the inputs. In this case it was assumed that the noise terms are distributionally invariant with respect to a compact matrix group of transformations. This assumption is very mild, as it is already satisfied in an i.i.d. setting (cf., the finite group of permutation matrices), however, if one has more knowledge about the noise terms, different transformation groups can also be used. In the case of measurement noises, our construction requires solving convex optimization problems. Besides having non-asymptotic theoretical guarantees, we proved that the resulting confidence bands are also strongly uniformly consistent. Next to that, a way to reduce the computational complexity was given, based on recursively computing the kernel matrix by using Schur complements. Both approaches were also demonstrated numerically, supporting their feasibility and comparisons with Gaussian Process Regression were presented, as well, for Gaussian and also for non-Gaussian measurement noises.

In order to generalize the result for the case without the assumption of a priori knowledge of the input distribution function, the kernel density estimation method was used to estimate the unknown density of the inputs. Similarly to the previous case, the task was first solved for noise-free outputs, then it was extended for measurement noises. As before, in the noise-free setting, the endpoints of the confidence intervals for an arbitrary query

input point can be obtained analytically. With measurement noises, convex optimization problems need to be solved. In both cases, the coverage guarantees of the bands become asymptotic, however, strong uniform consistency still holds true. Numerical experiments were provided for the noise-free and the noisy settings, as well.

Finally, based on the idea of the previous approaches, a method was proposed to single image inpainting and super-resolution problems. We called it SGKI, as it is based on simultaneously guaranteed kernel interpolations. Next to the value of the missing pixels, SGKI can also construct simultaneous, non-asymptotic, nonparametric confidence bands under the core assumption that the underlying data-generating function is from an RKHS having a continuous and universal kernel (it does not have to be band-limited). We showed that the uncertainty of the missing pixels can be quantified and a point estimate was also provided in the form of the minimum norm interpolant. We proved that the SGKI interpolant is always included in the confidence band, we argued that the approach can be extended to vector-valued outputs, needed to handle color images.

Several numerical experiments were also presented supporting the viability of the approach. For both the single image inpainting and super-resolution tasks, the SGKI method was compared with a variety of widespread methods. Quantitative results were given on a collection of synthetic images, which were randomly generated from a Paley-Wiener space, and also on real-world photos from the grayscale Set12 dataset. Finally, the uncertainty quantification capability of SGKI was illustrated and it was empirically demonstrated that SGKI can also be applied for color images.

Future research directions include the generalization of the proposed methods for other function spaces. While Paley-Wiener spaces play an important role in signal processing, other frameworks could prove interesting results for a wide range of other statistical and machine learning problems. The main difficulty of such generalization attempts comes from the need of constructing a stochastically guaranteed upper bound for the induced kernel norm of the unknown regression function. Our SGKI method for image restoration and super-resolution also has space for improvements, including the automatic tuning of its hyper-parameters, and improving its computational complexity.

Appendix

Boole's inequality, also known as the Union bound, is a consequence of σ -subadditivity, and it is a useful result for a countable collection of events [113, Theorem 1.2.11/b.]

Theorem A.1 (Boole's inequality) *If \mathbb{P} is a probability measure, then*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i\right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(A_i)$$

for any sequence of events A_1, A_2, \dots .

Hoeffding's inequality is a classical, well-known concentration inequality which provides an upper bound for the probability that the average of independent, bounded random variables deviates from their expected value [114, Theorem 2.8].

Theorem A.2 (Hoeffding) *Let X_1, \dots, X_n be independent random variables taking values from the intervals $[a_i, b_i], i = 1, \dots, n$. By defining the empirical mean by*

$$\bar{X}_n \doteq \frac{1}{n}(X_1 + \dots + X_n),$$

the following inequality holds:

$$\mathbb{P}(\bar{X}_n - \mathbb{E}(\bar{X}_n) \geq t) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{2n^2t^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i - a_i)^2}\right).$$

Now, we briefly overview a result about kernel density estimation.

Let x_1, \dots, x_n be a sample of n independent observations from a random variable \mathbb{X} with distribution $F(\mathbb{X}) = F(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and Lebesgue density $h_*(x) = h_*(x_1, \dots, x_n)$. In order to estimate h_* , the following function is considered:

$$\hat{h}_n(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n K_n(x, x_j),$$
$$K_n(x, X_j) = \frac{1}{b_n^m} k\left(\frac{1}{b_n}(x - x_j)\right),$$

where $k(u) = k(u_1, \dots, u_m)$ is a real-valued Borel-measurable function on \mathbb{R}^m such that

$$k(u) \text{ is a density on } \mathbb{R}^m \quad (4)$$

$$\sup_{u \in \mathbb{R}^m} k(u) < \infty \quad (5)$$

$$\|u\|^m k(u) \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } \|u\|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^m u_i^2 \rightarrow \infty \quad (6)$$

$$\int |c(t)| dt < \infty, \quad (7)$$

where

$$c(t) = \int \exp[it^T u] k(u) dt$$

is the characteristic function of $k(u)$ and $t^T u = \sum_{j=1}^m t_j u_j$.

$$g(a) = \int |c(at) - c(t)| dt \text{ is locally Lipschitz of order 1 at } a = 1. \quad (8)$$

Also, for the sequence $\{b_n\}$, the following conditions must hold:

$$b_n > 0, n = 1, 2, \dots, \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = 0, \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} nb_n \rightarrow \infty \quad (9)$$

$$b_n/b_{n+1} \rightarrow 1 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(nb_n^m)^2} < \infty \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{nb_n^{2m-1}} \left| \frac{1}{b_{n+1}} - \frac{1}{b_n} \right| < \infty \quad (12)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} nb_n^{2m} = \infty. \quad (13)$$

The next theorem guarantees uniform strong consistency in the multivariate case [115, Theorem 2.]

Theorem A.3 *Let $k(u)$ be such that (4), (5), (6), (7), (8) hold and $\{b_n\}$ be a sequence such that (9), (10), (11), (12), (13) hold. Then, if $f(x)$ is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R}^d , $\sup_x |\hat{h}_n(x) - h_*(x)| \rightarrow 0$ with probability one as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

The Hilbert projection theorem is a famous result in convex analysis, which can be used for any closed subspace of a Hilbert space [77, Theorem 4.11].

Theorem A.4 *Let M be a closed subspace of a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} .*

1. *Every $x \in \mathcal{H}$ has then a unique decomposition*

$$x = Px + Qx$$

into a sum of $Px \in M$ and $Qx \in M^\perp$.

2. Px and Qx are the nearest points to x in M and in M^\perp , respectively.

3. The mappings $P : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow M$ and $Q : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow M^\perp$ are linear.

4. $\|x\|^2 = \|Px\|^2 + \|Qx\|^2$.

The Shannon sampling theorem is a fundamental result of information theory. It states that a perfect reconstruction of a signal is possible if its band-limit is less than a given upper bound. Namely, if a function of time $f(t)$ is limited to the band from 0 to W cycles per second, it is completely determined giving its ordinates at a series of discrete points spaced $1/2W$ seconds apart [116, Theorem 13].

Theorem A.5 *Let $f(t)$ contain no frequencies over W . Then*

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} X_n \frac{\sin \pi(2Wt - n)}{\pi(2Wt - n)},$$

where $X_n = f(\frac{n}{2W})$.

By considering an optimization problem in the standard form given by

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f_0(x) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & f_i(x) \leq 0 \\ & h_j(x) = 0, \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

for $i = 1, \dots, m$, $j = 1, \dots, p$, where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathcal{D} = \cap_{i=1}^m \text{dom } f_i \cap \cap_{j=1}^p \text{dom } h_j$ is nonempty, the optimal value of (14) is denoted by p_* . Next, we define the Lagrange function associated with this task [78, Chapter 5, Subsections 5.1.1 and 5.1.2. and 5.2]

Definition A.1 (Lagrangian) *The Lagrangian $L : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ associated with problem (14) is*

$$L(x, \lambda, \nu) = f_0(x) + \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i f_i(x) + \sum_{j=1}^p \nu_j h_j(x),$$

where the domain of L is $\mathcal{D} \times \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^p$.

The variable λ_i is referred to as the *Lagrange multiplier* associated with the i -th inequality constraint $f_i(x) \leq 0$ and the variable ν_j is referred to as the *Lagrange multiplier* associated with the j -th equality constraint $h_j(x) = 0$.

Definition A.2 (Lagrange dual function) *The Lagrange dual function $g : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as the minimum value of the Lagrangian over x : for $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $\nu \in \mathbb{R}^p$,*

$$g(\lambda, \nu) = \inf_{x \in \mathcal{D}} L(x, \lambda, \nu).$$

Definition A.3 (Lagrange dual problem) *The following problem is called the Lagrange dual problem:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \max && g(\lambda, \nu) \\ & \text{subject to} && \lambda \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Definition A.4 (Weak duality) *The optimal value of the Lagrange dual problem, namely (15) is denoted by d_* . It is by definition, the best lower bound on p_* , which is the optimal value of (14). The inequality $d_* \leq p_*$ is called weak duality.*

Definition A.5 (Strong duality) *We say that strong duality holds, if $d_* = p_*$.*

$$\begin{aligned} & \min && f_0(x) \\ & \text{subject to} && f_i(x) \leq 0 \\ & && Ax = b, \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where $i = 1, \dots, m$ and f_0, \dots, f_m are convex, then the problem (16) is called convex.

Slater's condition provides a result for strong duality [78, Chapter 5, Subsection 5.2.3].

Theorem A.6 (Slater) *If an $x \in \mathcal{D}$ exists such that*

$$f_i(x) < 0, \quad i \in [m], \quad Ax = b, \tag{17}$$

then strong duality holds. (17) is called Slater's condition.

The Moore-Osgood theorem provides a sufficient condition for interchanging limits. One of its core requirements is the uniform convergence [117, Chapter 4, Theorem 2.]

Definition A.6 (Uniform convergence) *Suppose, that \mathcal{X} is a set and $\{f_n\}, n \in \mathbb{N}$, is a real-valued sequence of functions on \mathcal{X} . The sequence $\{f_n\}$ is **uniformly convergent** on \mathcal{X} with limit $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, $\exists n_0(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$, such that for every $n \geq n_0$:*

$$\sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}} |f_n(x) - f(x)| < \varepsilon.$$

Theorem A.7 (Moore-Osgood) *Let $\{a_{m,n}\}$ be a double sequence in a complete metric space (\mathcal{X}, ρ) . If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = b_m$ uniformly in m , and it holds that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = c_n$ for each n , then both $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} b_m$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} c_n$ exists and are equal to the double limit:*

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,m} = \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} a_{m,n}.$$

Definition A.7 (Nets) *If (\mathcal{F}, \leq) is a directed set, then for a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} , a net in \mathcal{H} is a collection of vectors $\{g_F\}_{F \in \mathcal{F}}$.*

Definition A.8 (Convergence in nets) *The net $\{g_F\}_{F \in \mathcal{F}}$ converges to $g \in \mathcal{H}$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $F_0 \in \mathcal{F}$ such that whenever $F_0 \leq F$. then $\|g - g_F\| < \varepsilon$.*

The following statement guarantees the convergence of nets for a setting in RKHSs [27, Statement 3.9.].

Theorem A.8 *Let \mathcal{H} be an RKHS on the set \mathbb{X} , let $g \in \mathcal{H}$ and for each finite set $F \subseteq X$, let $g_F = P_F(g)$, where P_F denotes the orthogonal projection of \mathcal{H} onto \mathcal{H}_F . Then the net $\{g_F\}_{F \in \mathcal{F}_X}$ converges in norm to g .*

Schwartz class is a class of smooth functions which vanish rapidly towards infinity [118, Definition 2.1.].

Definition A.9 (Schwartz class) *A function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is in the Schwartz class (denoted by $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$) if $f \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R})$ and for all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a constant $C_{m,n} > 0$ such that*

$$\rho_{m,n}(f) \doteq \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |x^m f^{(n)}(x)| = C_{m,n} < \infty.$$

Remark A.2 $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ is closed under addition of functions, multiplication of function by a scalar, differentiation of a function and under multiplication of functions.

The Fourier uncertainty principle shows that the spread of a function and its Fourier transform are inversely proportional [118, Theorem 1.1.].

Theorem A.9 (Fourier uncertainty principle) *For any $f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ and $x_0, \xi_0 \in \mathbb{R}$,*

$$\|f(x)\|_2^2 \leq 4\pi \|(x - x_0)f(x)\|_2 \|(\xi - \xi_0)\hat{f}(\xi)\|_2.$$

The Armein-Berthier theorem states that if a function has finite support, then the support of the Fourier transform of that function must be infinite [118, Theorem 1.3.].

Theorem A.10 (Armein-Berthier) *Let $f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ and $E, F \subset \mathbb{R}$ be sets of finite measure. Then*

$$\|f\|_{L^2(\mathbb{R})} \leq C(\|f\|_{L^2(E^c)} + \|\hat{f}\|_{L^2(E^c)})$$

for some constant C that only depends on E and F .

The continuous mapping theorem states that if a sequence of random vectors converge to a certain value, then the convergence still holds if the random vectors and their limit are arguments of a continuous function [119, Theorem 7.24].

Theorem A.11 (Continuous mapping) *Let (\mathbb{D}, d) and (\mathbb{E}, e) be metric spaces. Let $g_n : \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}$ be a sequence of maps which satisfy the following: if $x_n \rightarrow x$ with $x_n \in \mathbb{D}$, then $g_n(x_n) \rightarrow g(x)$, where $g : \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}$. Let X_n be maps taking values in \mathbb{D} and let X be Borel measurable and separable with $\mathbb{P}(X \in \mathbb{D}) = 1$. Then,*

$$1. X_n \xrightarrow{d} X \implies g_n(X_n) \xrightarrow{d} g(X),$$

$$2. X_n \xrightarrow{p} X \implies g_n(X_n) \xrightarrow{p} g(X),$$

$$3. X_n \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} X \implies g_n(X_n) \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} g(X),$$

where \xrightarrow{d} means convergence in distribution, \xrightarrow{p} means convergence in probability, $\xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}}$ means almost sure convergence.

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